

H2020 - INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP - Leadership in enabling and industrial technologies - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

ICT-11-2017 Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation – Innovation Action (IA)

CHILD
RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D2.3 - Privacy and Anonymisation Methodological Foundations

Workpackage:	WP2 – Grassroot Collective Intelligence in the Missing Children Investigation
Authors:	UBITECH, SLG, NTUA
Status:	Final
Date:	28/09/2018
Version:	1.0
Classification:	Public

Disclaimer:

The ChildRescue project is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme of the European Union. This document reflects only authors' views. The EC is not liable for any use that may be done of the information contained therein

ChildRescue Project Profile

Grant Agreement No.: 780938

Acronym:	ChildRescue
Title:	Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue
URL:	http://www.childrescue.eu
Start Date:	01/01/2018
Duration:	36 months

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Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks
0.1	30/06/2018	Danai Vergeti (UBITECH), Dimitris Ntalaperas (UBITECH) Nefeli Bountouni (SingularLogic)	ToC
0.2	30/07/2018	Dimitris Ntalaperas (UBITECH)	First Draft
0.3	28/08/2018	Nefeli Bountouni (SingularLogic)	Internal review
0.4	29/08/2018	Ariadni Michalitsi – Psarrou (NTUA)	Internal review
0.5	17/9/2018	Dimitris Ntalaperas, Danai Vergeti (UBITECH)	Addressing comments of SILO, NTUA and 1 st review from EAB members.
0.6	26/9/2018	Dimitris Ntalaperas, Danai Vergeti (UBITECH)	Addressing comments from the 2 nd review from the EAB members.
0.65	27/9/2018	Ariadni Michalitsi – Psarrou, Dimitris Varoutas, Eleni Kanellou (NTUA)	Added Ethics Advisory Board Report
0.7	28/9/2018	Dimitris Ntalaperas, Danai Vergeti (UBITECH)	Final version for QC
0.8	28/9/2018	Minas Pertselakis (S5)	WP level check
1.0	29/9/2018	Christos Ntanos, Dimitris Varoutas (NTUA)	Quality Review

Executive Summary

ChildRescue will have to store and process personal data belonging both to stakeholders and to users of the platform. It has, therefore, to employ the necessary techniques, to ensure that data privacy is respected. Since the adoption of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) by all member states of the European Union (EU), all parties that handle and store personal data, referred to as data controllers, and parties that perform processing of said data, referred to as data processors, need to conform to specific guidelines that govern both the storage and processing of data and the ability and rights of data subjects to control their stored data. The present document covers the main techniques that will be employed by ChildRescue to ensure private data protection and GDPR compliance.

At first, a review of the most commonly-used encryption and anonymisation techniques is given. Storing and processing data requires that certain guidelines of the GDPR are respected; these guidelines are briefly reviewed and the way ChildRescue conforms with these guidelines is outlined. Finally, the technical details of the modules that will handle storage and processing of personal data is presented. The modules implement all the guidelines, put forth by the requirements of the GDPR, therefore making the ChildRescue platform GDPR compliant at the technical level.

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1 Introduction

Conforming to the established legislature and respecting stakeholder's and physical person's sensitive information is a major requirement and challenge for every process, framework or application that deals with storage or processing of personal data. With the advent and adoption of the GDPR by all member states of the EU, the set of requirements, that each party that deals with personal data must fulfil, has been defined in a much stricter sense than before. Moreover, data regulation under the GDPR has been extended to not only cover the kind of data stored, but also explicitly define the rights of a physical person whose personal data are stored, commonly referred to as data subject under the GDPR terminology, *after* her/his consent is given and her/his data are stored. Under the present regulation, a data subject can revoke any consent given at any time and request that any stored personal data be removed. In general, data subjects now have the right to be aware of any details about how their data are processed, analysed, shared or used in decision-making and analytics and have moreover the right to access and/or erase these data.

ChildRescue deals heavily with personal and sensitive data. The data subjects contain among others both stakeholders, like missing or unaccompanied children, and registered citizens that will act as the social network of ChildRescue. Apart from using the data subject's data and feedback for the resolution of cases, the participating organisations, and thus ChildRescue, also use these data for statistical analysis of past cases, something that falls under the term of processing under the definitions of GDPR. Moreover, ChildRescue will also use algorithms based on profile data that will provide suggestions to organisation operators concerning the best route of actions. Such tasks fall under the definition of profiling and decision-making of the GDPR.

Citizens that will use the ChildRescue platform to aid with cases of missing children will effectively contribute to investigation procedures by offering evidence. Processing of this kind of data falls within the conditions of lawful processing as these are presented in Article 6 of the GDPR; namely the "performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller". Authorities may need both to be able to track back the evidence to the citizen that generated it, both for legal reasons and for further direct communication that may be needed, and to avert abuse of the platform from users with evil intent. For that reason, a Know Your Customer (KYC) infrastructure will be deployed for ChildRescue, so that each citizen will go through an identification process before registering.

This deliverable documents the ways in which ChildRescue protects sensitive data and how it conforms to the GDPR by providing the necessary means of control to data subjects. Section 2 provides the working methodology. Section 3 briefly overviews the main techniques currently used for anonymising and encrypting data, while also describing the ways that these techniques can be used to fully conform to the GDPR. Section 4 gives a detailed overview of how the proposed techniques will be implemented in the context of ChildRescue. Section 5 finally, provides the main conclusions of the present work.

2 Working Methodology

In order to identify the specifications of the privacy and anonymisation framework ChildRescue, the following deliverables were used as input: "D1.1 – User Requirements", "D1.2 – Regulatory Framework for Data Protection, Privacy and Ethical Issues" and "D1.3 – ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release 1". D1.1 and D1.3 provide the functional and non-functional requirements and use cases that the privacy and anonymisation framework need to address, while D1.2 provides the main outlines that the framework needs to follow in order to be compliant with the GDPR.

2.1 Privacy and Anonymisation Framework technical requirements

The following tables show how the functional and non-functional requirements and use cases from D1.1, as well as, the procedures described in D1.3 are mapped to the technical requirements of the ChildRescue Privacy and Anonymisation Framework.

Table 2-1 Requirements mapping to technical requirements of the Privacy and Anonymisation Framework

Requirement	Description	Framework requirement	Relevant data
FR_5	ChildRescue must allow users to anonymise data	The framework must provide anonymisation of the data	User data, case data
FR_11	ChildRescue must provide a user with the ability to register with a pseudonym	The framework must provide pseudonymisation	User data
NFR_4	ChildRescue must be able to protect any personal data stored	The framework must provide anonymisation and security of the data	User data, case data
NFR_5	ChildRescue must be able to encrypt any data transmitted	The framework must provide encryption of the exchanged data	User data, case data, other data
NFR_7	ChildRescue must be able to archive any significant data required by the user	The framework must provide anonymisation and encryption of the data	Case data

Table 2-2 Use cases mapping to technical requirements of the Privacy and Anonymisation Framework

Use case	Description	Framework requirement	Relevant data
VU.08	to send feedback in the form of text, image or video the	The framework must provide encryption of the exchanged data	User data, case data, other data

	Organisation concerning a missing child by filling-in an appropriate form		
SU.01, RT.01, VT.01, FM.01	to be able to specify some basic, optional personal profile information during the initial registration process	The framework must provide pseudonymisation of the data	User data
FM.02	to be able to fill in extended profiling information about an unaccompanied migrant minor residing in the premises	The framework must provide pseudonymisation of the data	Case data
CM.01	to be able to fill in the basic information about a new missing child case	The framework must provide pseudonymisation of the data	Case data
CM.02	to update the information of a case with more details or specify crucial information (like location last seen, latest info gathered, etc.)	The framework must provide pseudonymisation of the data	Case data
OO.8	to have an overview of the duration of all historical cases and the human resources assigned on each one	The framework must provide pseudonymisation of the data	Case data

Table 2-3 ChildRescue processes mapping to technical requirements of the Privacy and Anonymisation Framework

Process	Description	Framework requirement	Relevant data
Preparation and Profiling	Construction of a multilayer profile of the missing person	The framework must provide pseudonymisation of the data	Case data
Coordination and Collaboration	Real-time sharing of information and communication among team members	The framework must provide pseudonymisation of the data	User data, Case data
Action	The investigation process followed after report of a missing child or a tracing request for an unaccompanied minor	The framework must provide pseudonymisation of the data	User data, Case data
Archiving	Case closure in a secure and a privacy-respectful manner	The framework must provide anonymisation and encryption of the data	User data, Case data

In the aforementioned tables the user data refer to the personal data of the end users, while the case data contain the missing children/unaccompanied minor personal information and any additional case or evidence data.

Based on the above tables the ChildRescue Privacy and Anonymisation Framework should provide anonymisation and pseudonymisation techniques for the user data and the case data. Additionally, encryption should also be implemented during the exchange of information among the various stakeholders through the ChildRescue Platform. The ARX Anonymisation Framework¹ addresses the aforementioned requirements, while Public Key Infrastructure covers the needs for encryption of the data. A detailed presentation of the methodologies and the technologies that are going to be used in the ChildRescue Privacy and Anonymisation Framework is provided in section 4.

2.2 Future versions

The next versions of this deliverable (D2.4, D2.5) will present the various access policies on the data based on the user roles that will be defined in WP3, the secure exchange of data between the components of the architecture defined in WP3, as well as, the authentication and authorisation methodologies.

¹ ARX – Data Anonymisation Tool: <https://arx.deidentifier.org/development/framework/>

3 Landscape analysis in privacy and anonymisation

In the present section, an overview of the main existing techniques for anonymising and encrypting data is given. Additionally, approaches on the identification of the users are also provided. The extent to which these techniques can be used to conform with GDPR requirements will also be described, before moving to the details regarding how these techniques will be used in the context of ChildRescue, which will be given in Section 3.

3.1 Background

When data are communicated between two parties, it is often a requirement that the contents of the communication remain secret to non-participating parties. Encryption techniques that tried to provide the required security were used since antiquity, usually to protect military secrets. Nowadays, personal sensitive data are also a main focus for data encryption; whenever two parties need to exchange information in such a way so that the contents remain hidden from eavesdroppers, an encryption scheme must be applied. Furthermore, when a party communicates with another party, each party needs to be able to verify that the other party is who it claims to be and not a pretender. The techniques used for both encryption and identity verification (via the so-called digital signature), typically involve the employment of similar techniques, which fall under the domain of cryptography.

Apart from encryption, there are cases where the data contain both informational content that needs to be communicated publicly and personal data that need to remain inaccessible. There is no meaning to encrypt for example the measurements and results that take place in a medical study, as these need to be accessible by all interested researchers. The personal data of the patients involved however, should not be disclosed. In these cases, techniques that perform data masking on the original data set need to be applied. The main difference between encryption and data masking is that a masked data set is in plain format and can be read by anyone but cannot be reversed to the original data in any way. In data masking, data privacy protection is ensured storing or transmitting masked data, without disclosing the transformations performed. In the case of ChildRescue, many messages need to be broadcasted publicly or in an extended network of people. Missing children alerts, and evidence created by citizens acting as social sensors are examples of such messages. Performing data masking to these data ensures that only relevant information is transmitted publicly, whereas irrelevant data that contain personal information are hidden.

Before proceeding with an analysis of the existing techniques, the definition of the terms pseudonymisation and anonymisation is going to be provided as these are used in most legal documents and especially in the GDPR.

- **Pseudonymisation** means the transformation of data in such a way so that personal data cannot be retrieved without the usage of additional identifiers, not present in the transformed set.
- **Anonymisation** means the transformation of data in such a way so that personal data cannot be retrieved in any way from the transformed set.

The definition covers all types of data transformation so, technically, encryption can be used both for pseudonymisation (by keeping the decryption key in a separate database) and for anonymisation (by dropping the key or using one-way hashes). However, in the present section, we will cover encryption

separately and we will focus on data masking techniques only when discussing pseudonymisation and anonymisation.

3.2 Techniques & methodologies

3.2.1 Data pseudonymisation and anonymisation

It is often the case that data that concern individuals need to be communicated publicly. Examples of such cases are medical studies, poll results and, in the case of ChildRescue, data about missing children. While personal information is inevitably disclosed in these cases, it is necessary to restrict the amount of data published or stored to the bare minimum needed for each case. When personal identification is not needed, the data disclosed should be such that no identification can be performed by reverse engineering, ensuring effectively that the people described by data remain anonymous.

Data anonymisation can be performed by a variety of techniques, that are not needed to be performed exclusively [1]. The first step in anonymising the data set is performing removal or encryption of personal identifiable information (PII) [2]; these include information like name, address, id number etc. The mapping to the original data can be maintained in a separate database in case of pseudonymisation or be entirely discarded for anonymisation.

Removal of PII often is not enough for ensuring privacy however, since combinations of other information can still lead to the identification of a person, especially if said combinations occur rarely in the original data set. Combinations of *Personal Characteristics* data (also called Quasi-identifying attributes), like ethnicity and sex, are typically such combinations. If, for example, a single combination of a certain nationality, sex and marital status appears in a data set, this certain person can be identified by only requiring the extra knowledge that she/he is a member of the data set. Anonymising a set that contains personal characteristics data typically involves one or more of the techniques of **data masking**, namely a) encryption, b) shuffling, c) substitution, d) variance, e) masking and f) pruning. Encryption, as already mentioned, is covered in a different section.

Shuffling is the technique of randomly or via an algorithm, changing the values of a data column. The transformed data contain entries that cannot lead to the person's identification since the information contained in each row are now invalid. The transformed data sets may also, depending on the case, keep its main statistical characteristics and still be useful for statistical analysis. Shuffling has the drawback that when performed as the single anonymisation technique, can leave the transformed data set open to reverse engineering attempts, especially when the shuffling algorithm is known.

Substitution is similar to shuffling, the main difference being that the substituted values do not originate from values occurring in other entries of the data set, but rather in external lists. A list of all the ethnicities for example may be used to randomly change the ethnicity of an entry. In contrast with shuffling, this may lead to the appearance of values not appearing in the original data set.

Variance is typically applied to values of numerical nature and consist of adding or subtracting a random noise to the value; an example is to compute a random number between -5% and 5% of a person's height and add/subtract this to the original value. The variance technique can too lead to the formation of data sets that keep their original statistical characteristics, if the mean value of the random noise added is zero.

Masking is the substitution of all, or part of, the value of a field with null values or a standard character. It is typically used in credit card numbers where the unmasked fields can be used to identify details like type of card (VISA or MasterCard), but numbers unique to the individual person are being left out. Masking also applies to non-text data, like images or video. Substituting the face of minors in media pictures is a typical case of image masking.

Pruning is simply the deletion of a record. Pruning can be used in records that have rare combinations and are thus easier to be traced back to a certain person. As these combinations are rare, the statistical properties of the data will not be affected much, however there is the drawback that such combinations often have scientific value. A special case of pruning is the deletion of only certain values of a record by removing columns or assigning null values; this last technique is also called nulling. Nulling is efficient for discarding personal data that are not needed for processing but has the drawback that it can draw suspicion that data masking has been performed on the data set.

Except from Masking, all anonymisation techniques can be used in such a way that the transformed data set, though technically contains false data, appears realistic to an outside viewer.

Figure 1 depicts an example of data masking, with each column being affected by the transformation being denoted by the purple outline. Except from the masked credit card number and the null ages, all other values appear realistic. However, the combinations of name and sex lead to a male Helen and a female Jack which do not appear realistic. Data masking algorithms can be designed such that realistic looking combinations and values are produced in the transformed data set. The set of all the transformations performed defines a transformation matrix; the inverse of this transformation matrix may be used to restore the original data. When the transformation matrix is stored in a separate database, the data set is considered pseudonymised, whereas, if it is deleted, it is considered as anonymised.

Figure 1: Example of data masking

3.2.1.1 Data anonymisation models for dealing with attackers having access to multiple data sets

Though in the previous sections we analysed the common masking techniques, the degree of anonymisation often depends not only on the efficiency of the transformation themselves, but to the extent that an attacker possesses knowledge of extra datasets containing information of the data subjects. These datasets may be also anonymised, but when combined they could be used to de-identify the subject(s); a typical example involves combination with clinical data released as anonymous with a public voter dataset [6]. To handle these cases, a set of privacy models have been suggested;

each one attempts to quantify the degree of anonymisation to one or more metrics and transform the data set in a way that target values of the metrics are achieved.

In the following sub-sections a brief overview of the most commonly used models will be given.

3.2.1.1.1 k-anonymity

A data set is k -anonymous if each entry from the released data set cannot be distinguished from at least $k-1$ other entries. The distinction is based on the number of attributes identified as personal characteristics (also called quasi-identifiers). Each group that shares the same values of the quasi-identifiers is called an equivalence class. Figure 2 depicts an example of a k -anonymous set with $k=2$. Here, a set of four attributes have been designated as quasi-identifiers, namely the race, birth year, gender and postal code (which is masked).

To achieve k -anonymity two techniques are commonly being employed:

- Suppression, is similar to masking and assigns a generic single value to a variable. This can be like the masked postal code of the example or a fake value if a realistic look of the data is needed
- Generalisation, in which groups of values are merged into one. For example, birthdates can be grouped into decades so that any birthdate from 1980 to 1989 being assigned the value of 1980.

Race	Birth	Gender	Postal Code	Diabetes
White	1980	male	20*	Yes
White	1980	male	20*	No
White	1980	male	20*	Yes
White	1982	female	18*	Yes
White	1982	female	18*	Yes
Black	1982	male	18*	Yes
Black	1982	male	18*	No

Figure 2: Example of a k -anonymous set with $k=2$ and three equivalent classes

One of the main problems of k -anonymity is that efficient generalisation depends on the proximity of values. If values are very dispersed, broad categories should be used to achieve a high value of k , and this leads to degradation of data (the data loses its usefulness to the recipients instead of only to the attackers).

Another issue is that what is considered a non quasi-identifier by the holder of the data may be effectively be a quasi-identifier in the hands of an attacker. In the example given, diabetes is not part of the quasi-identifier set and was not transformed under k -anonymisation. However, attributes not transformed may exhibit a lack of diversity; if this is the case the attacker may use this to expose sensitive information. In the example given, the attacker may know that "Alice" is white and was born in 1982. Though the attacker cannot distinguish which of the two rows (4 or 5) correspond to Alice,

she/he will know that Alice has diabetes. The problem can be remedied by considering *Diabetes* to be quasi-identifier too, however this tends to aggravate the problem of efficient generalisation described above.

As a final note, we should also mention an extension of *k-anonymity* model, namely the *k-map*. Similar to *k-anonymity*, the *k-map* requires that the entries cannot be distinguished from at least $k-1$ entries, in the case of *k-map* however the records counted correspond to the larger population and only to those present in the data set and thus the computed k values are adjusted accordingly along with the characteristics of the relevant transformations. Consider for example the postal code as a quasi-identifier and that we perform k -anonymity with $k=5$. Suppose further that a postal code appears in the dataset that corresponds to a town with 20 registered residents. An attacker can identify this, and reduce her/his search space greatly. To remedy this, we can mask the postal code. While this transformation may not alter the k -value relative to the original data set, it will greatly increase it relevant to the larger population

3.2.1.1.2 l-diversity

With l -diversity only equivalent classes that have a certain amount of diversity in their sensitive data are contained in the data set. The diversity is measured by the parameter l and there are various ways to define the measure of “ l -diversity” [7]:

- distinct: where each equivalent class is required to have at least l distinct values in their sensitive data
- entropy: where the entropy of each equivalent class E denoted by $Entropy(E)$, is greater or equal to the logarithm of l . $Entropy(E)$ is defined as: $Entropy(E) = -\sum_s p(E,s)\log(p(E,s))$ with $p(E,s)$ being the fraction of records in E that have the sensitive value s .
- (c- l) recursive: where the counts $n(E,s_i)$ are computed for each equivalent class and each distinct sensitive value s_i (so that $n(E,s_1)$ is the number of times that s_1 appears in E , $n(E,s_2)$ is the number of times that s_2 appears in E , and so on). The counts are then sorted in descending order and a constant c is chosen. If n_{max} is the first element of the list of sorted counts, (c- l) reclusiveness requires that: $n_{max} \leq c \sum_{n \neq n_{max}} n$

For the example of Figure 2, if distinct diversity is chosen, the data set has a diversity equal to one.

Though l -diversity achieves better results in terms of anonymisation than simple k -anonymity, it too can have its limitation depending on the characteristics of the data set. If a sensitive value is very rare (e.g. a rare disease), it is difficult to achieve a high value of l . Furthermore, the equivalent classes may be low when compared to the count of the data entries to achieve a satisfactory value of l . For 10000 entries for example, we must have a maximum of 100 equivalent classes to achieve an l value equal to 2. As a final note, *l-diversity* does not distinguish between the semantics of sensitive values. This has as a result that entries are considered diverse although semantically they are not. Consider the example depicted in Figure 3. Although the equivalent class has a diversity equal to 2, an attacker with partial information may infer that “Alice” has a serious medical condition.

Race	Birth	Gender	Postal Code	Condition
White	1982	female	18*	HIV+
White	1982	female	18*	Breast Cancer

Figure 3: Example of diverse, yet semantically linked, sensitive information

3.2.1.1.3 t-closeness

Intuitively, an equivalent is defined to have t -closeness relative to a sensitive attribute, if the distribution that the sensitive attribute has in the equivalent class, is similar to the one it has in the whole data set. More precisely, if the distance between the distribution of the sensitive variable in the equivalent class and the distribution of the sensitive variable in the data set is at most t , then the equivalent class has t -closeness relative to the attribute. If all of the equivalent classes have t -closeness, then the whole data set is said to also have t -closeness.

t -closeness ensures a good level of anonymity on the data, however it has the common problem of all anonymisation techniques, mainly that what is considered sensitive data may in fact be a quasi-identifier in the hands of the attacker. For example an attacker could, by external means, know that a person has some, yet unknown, medical condition and search the data set to identify the exact condition or at least narrow down the list.

3.2.1.1.4 δ -presence

For an equivalent class, δ_E is defined as the ratio between the size of an equivalent class that is present in a dataset and the size of the same equivalent class as this is considered in the general population. Consider as an extreme case that a town with postal code equal to 12345 has a total of five residents and that a dataset contains 4 subjects with the same postal code. Then we know that 4 out of the 5 who live in that town are part of the dataset. In numbers the δ_E parameter for this equivalent class has a value of $4/5$, or 80%. In effect, δ_E is the ratio between the k -anonymous and k -map equivalent classes.

It is evident that for anonymised data sets, the δ_E for each equivalent class, should be the smallest possible. In essence, if we define the δ of the data set to be the maximum value of the δ values of each equivalent classes, then δ should be as low as possible.

Although δ is a great indicator for anonymisation, the main difficulty lies with estimating the data set that represents the larger population. This data set is, in many cases, not available so that estimations may be given by the data experts.

It is noteworthy that δ -presence, as originally was proposed [8], involved the computation of two δ parameters: δ_{max} , which is the same described above and δ_{min} , which was the *minimum* value of the δ values of each equivalent classes. This was to compensate for symmetry attacks, namely attacks that were based on the knowledge that someone was *not* in the case. However, this case is not encountered frequently in practice.

3.2.1.2 Data Anonymisation via aggregation

A special case of data anonymisation is when only aggregated data are needed and information corresponding to specific individuals is of no concern. If, for example, a survey needs to check for correlations between nutrition habits and specific health markers, once the correlations are obtained the original data in row format are no longer needed. It is, thus, possible to store only the aggregated data needed for correlations and discard the original data set; the aggregated data can be considered as anonymised.

One common technique for data aggregation is the Data Cube [4]. A Data Cube as an $m_1 \times m_2 \times \dots \times m_n$ array, with n being the number of aggregated variables and m_i being the number of distinct values the variable indexed by i can take. Figure 4 depicts an example of a Data Cube for the case of $n=3$, storing the aggregate values concerning disappearance incidents of children. The variables are *Financial Status*, *Family Status* and *Age* and indexed appropriately. For example, an index of zero for the Financial Status can mean that the child's family is in extreme poverty, an index of 1 for Family Status can mean that the parents of the child are divorced and an index of 1 for the Age may correspond to the age of 6. If we name the Data Cube matrix as *DC*, in such a scheme the value stored in cell indexed as $DC[0][1][1]$ will contain the number of disappeared children, who came from a family with divorced parents, who live under extreme poverty and who were of age 6 when they disappeared. In similar way, $DC[0][1][2]$ may mean the number of disappeared children, who came from a family with divorced parents, who live under extreme poverty and who were of age 7 when they disappeared, and so on. If a certain combination has a very low count when compared to the average value, then we discern that this combination is a rare one and can lead to identification of the subject's details. Such combinations are thus dropped. For further security a random small noise with a mean value of zero can be added to each cell, so that the data set is further obfuscated.

Figure 4: Data Cube Example

The technical description of the data pseudonymisation and anonymisation approaches that are adopted by the ChildRescue platform are provided in section 4.1.

3.2.2 Pseudonyms

Broadly speaking, a pseudonym is a set of artificial identifiers that replace PII. In contrast with anonymisation of PII covered in the previous section, pseudonyms are mainly applicable to users of a service of platform and are typically used to cover the personal details of a platform user, as she/he appears on the platform. These personal details do not only cover the typical PII, like name, address etc., but also details of usage that can be linked back to the user. The subject's IP address for example, can be used to trace back her/his location and should therefore be hidden when using a pseudonym. Usage of pseudonym is required when there is a need that a subject appears under a false identity. The identity of an informant contacting the police for example, should remain secret to the public, however the police should be able to identify her/him.

Apart from GDPR compliance, the usage of pseudonyms is critical when the identity of a user needs to be protected; in ChildRescue this is very important for when a citizen, who contacts the organisations or authorities for providing evidence or new information, needs to be able to retain her/his anonymity. Typically, pseudonyms are generated via an IP masking infrastructure such as TOR. Users negotiate a key to establish a secure connection with the pseudonym issuing authority; this authority is typically the platform that implements the pseudonym infrastructure. The authority issues a certificate for the pseudonym, which is then used by the user for authenticating her/his pseudo-identity. The authority keeps the correspondence between the personal identity and the pseudo-identity and appropriately authorises the pseudo-user and audits her/his activities to discern any attempt of pseudonym hijacking. The technical description for the pseudonym generation approach adopted by the ChildRescue platform is provided in section 4.2.

3.2.3 Encryption

Encryption of data refers to a set of techniques that can be used between two parties to exchange information in a secure and reliable way. This means that data exchanged between them are:

- Encrypted: No other party can make sense of the data unless the other party has possession of the private key needed to decipher the information.
- Signed: The identity of a sender can be verified in a way that the recipient is sure that the sender is who she/he claims to be. Upon receipt of the message, the sender cannot deny that the message originated by her/him and cannot claim that the contents of the message were others than those received by the receiver.

Apart from data exchange, encryption can also be used when storing data. There are two kinds of encryption, the symmetric/private key and the public key encryption. In symmetric key encryption, the key for both encryption and decryption is the same and is shared between communicating parties. Public key encryption on the other hand relies on the existence of two keys: one public and one private. The public key is used for encryption and, as its name implies, is publicly shared. Anyone who wishes to send an encrypted message to the receiver, does so by using the public key. The private key is kept at the receiver's side only and is inaccessible by the public. The receiver uses the private key to decrypt the message.

In general, public key encryption is used more widely. It has several benefits over symmetric encryption, most notably the fact that communicating does not require the exchange of keys beforehand, a process

that can be both time-consuming and introduce additional risk. The general principles of generating and using public keys for cryptography are depicted in the next three figures.

Figure 5 depicts the process of generating a private/public key pair. The subject uses a key generation algorithm which generates a key pair. Key pair generation algorithms typically make use of large random numbers; the main idea behind most public key cryptography algorithms is that though multiplication of two large numbers is a computationally easy process, the reverse procedure, factoring a product of two large prime numbers, is an intractable process. After generating a key pair, this key pair can be used for secure communication and digital signing as depicted in Figure 6 and Figure 7 respectively. In the first case, anyone wishing to communicate with the receiver, uses the receiver's public key to encrypt the message. Upon receipt of the encrypted message, also called a cipher, the receiver can use her/his private key to decrypt the message. In the digital signing case on the other hand, the sender uses her/his own private key to sign the message. The receiver, upon getting the signed document, uses the sender's public key to obtain the original document. If any modification was made while the message was en-route, the verification procedure will fail.

Figure 5: Public Private Key pair generation

Figure 6: Encryption and Decryption of a message under the public key encryption scheme

Figure 7: Digital signature under the public key encryption scheme

Although the main mechanisms of public cryptography are simple, when a large network of users are being connected and wish to exchange information securely, it can be quite difficult to distribute public keys in such a way such that the end users can be sure that the party publishing the public key is the actual owner of the public key. In order to distribute public keys securely, networks are usually called to implement what is commonly known as a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI). A PKI can create, distribute and revoke digital certificates, which are digital documents that prove the ownership of a public key. The establishment of a binding between an entity and a public key is verified by the Certificate Authority (CA). The CA issues certificates, provided that registration was carried through correctly. The

confirmation of correct registration is done by the Registration Authority (RA), which in many cases can be the same organisation as the CA. A third entity, called the Voucher Authority (VA), can vouch on behalf of the CA for the validity of the entity's information. Though a VA can reject a party's request if validation fails, it cannot issue or revoke the certificate; this is solely the responsibility of the CA.

Once the communicating parties can share public keys in a trustworthy manner, a security protocol can be used to encrypt communication. The Transport Layer Security (TLS) and the soon to be deprecated Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) are the most common examples of such protocols. Under TSL, before initiating exchange of data, a handshake between parties must first take place. In the handshake at least one party (the server) provides its certificate thus proving its identity. After validation, both parties generate and exchange keys and encrypt their messages using a private key algorithm. Figure 8 depicts an example of a PKI setup.

Figure 8: Typical PKI Infrastructure

3.2.4 Know Your Customer (KYC)

It is required by law for many legal entities to verify the identity of each potential customer/applicant before engaging to any transaction with her/him. Identification is a very old process and in the most common case, it involves the presentation of an official identification document (typically an id card) that is presented by the customer in person. The entity compares the visual appearance of the person to the one depicted in the picture of the id card and, if matched, confirms that the data contained in the id card are valid and the person is who she/he claims to be.

Such processes, typically called "Know You Customer" (KYC), though simple, may be difficult to implement electronically. Though no standards exist yet, the most straightforward approach is to perform the exact same steps required for physical identification, with any exchange of information

being performed electronically. The verification procedure itself may be performed either by an operator that will compare the images provided, or automatically via an algorithm; even in the latter case, however, the algorithm's result needs to be verified by a physical person.

Figure 9: An example of a KYC Infrastructure Setup.

Figure 9 depicts a sample KYC Infrastructure Setup. The platform/application asks the applicant for a picture of herself/himself; for a mobile application this can be easily done via a selfie. Then a picture of an ID is required, which typically involves taking two pictures for the two faces of the identification card. The images are uploaded in the identification database; the identification is carried out either by an automated process or by the operator; both cases are depicted in the Figure. The applicant is informed accordingly for the result of the identification.

3.3 GDPR Compliance

Since the adoption of GDPR by all member states of the EU, the processes of storing, handling and transmitting data need to conform to specific rules in order to be considered GDPR compliant. Under the GDPR any entity that handles personal data is fully accountable for conforming to the GDPR and responsible for any data breaches.

Entities that store and process personal data are referred to in the GDPR as *data controllers*. The exact definition as this appears in Article 4 of the GDPR reads: "*controller*' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law;"

An entity that does not collect personal data itself, but processes it on behalf of a controller is termed under the GDPR as *processor*. The exact definition of a processor as this appears in the GDPR is given as: "*processor*' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller;"

While listing the complete set of rules of GDPR is outside the scope of the present deliverable, controllers and processors should follow a set of guidelines. These guidelines are summarised as follows:

- **Legitimate interest:** To store data that contain personal information, the controller should have a legitimate and valid reason to do so. In the context of ChildRescue this is typically covered by the existing procedures of the participating organisations and are followed “as is” in ChildRescue. SoC for example has a legitimate reason to publish a child’s personal data under an Amber Alert, a procedure that is regulated by the existing legislature.
- **Provision of Consent:** Storing personal information of an individual requires that the said individual will give her/his consent.
- **Right to be forgotten:** An individual cannot only revoke his consent at any time, but she/he may request that any personal information already stored be removed upon request. In case of erroneous data, the individual may request correction of data.
- **Right of access:** Any processing of an individual’s data must be approved by her/him.
- **Data breaches:** When any compromise of the system leads to personal data exposure, the supervisory authority should be notified promptly within 72 hours both of the occurrence of the breach and of the details concerning which data have been exposed.
- **Anonymisation:** GDPR encourages controllers to perform pseudonymisation on data before they are stored.
- **Sharing by third parties:** Explicit consent must be given before personal data can be shared with third parties. The consent may be revoked at any time.

As already mentioned, the establishment of Legitimate Interest in the case of ChildRescue derives from the existing procedures, agreements between the participating organisations and the public sector and the existing legislature. Details can be found at the Regulatory Framework of ChildRescue that is documented in deliverable D1.2. Legitimate Interest will therefore not be covered in the present deliverable. Sharing by third parties will also not take place in ChildRescue, so that point is also omitted.

For each of the rest aspects, we will give a brief review and describe how ChildRescue will conform to its requirements in the following subsections. The details of the implementation of the proposed techniques will be given in Section 4.

3.3.1 Pseudonymisation and anonymisation in GDPR

Pseudonymisation in the context of GDPR is defined as “the processing of personal data in such a way that the data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information.” Under GDPR, data controllers are encouraged to perform pseudonymisation on any stored data. Data that are truly anonymised can be used, under circumstances, beyond the strict confines of “specific, explicit and legitimate purposes”. Furthermore, access, rectification and erasure need not be provided to data subjects if their data is anonymised.

As already mentioned, the GDPR makes a distinction between pseudonymisation and anonymisation by distinguishing between data that can be re-identified and data that cannot be re-identified. Re-identifiable data are those covered by the term “pseudonymisation”. Pseudonymised data are typically stored using data masking and/or encryption. When encrypted, parties that do not have possession of the private key cannot discern the informational content of the original data set. When data masking is performed on the other hand, parties have access to data that have no relevance to the original data

set. In both encrypted and data masking cases however, it is vital that the key and the data transformation matrix is kept somewhere, preferably in an external and secure data base. If they are not, the original data set may not be reconstructed in any way and the data set may not be classified as "pseudonymised" but rather as "anonymised".

Data sets that are truly "anonymised" are those for which the encryption keys and/or the transformation matrices have been deleted. Since there is no way to obtain confidential information from these data sets, anonymised data are not covered by the GDPR. However, anonymised data may still be very useful, especially when only statistical information is needed from a raw data set. In such scenarios, the data set may be transformed by using a combination of the techniques put forth in Section 2.1.1 so that although the data set is obfuscated, the statistical characteristics remain mostly intact.

ChildRescue will conform to the guidelines put forth by the GDPR by performing pseudonymisation to any personal data that are allowed to be stored under the Regulatory Framework or under the data subject's explicit consent. When data expire, or consent is revoked, ChildRescue will provide the functionality to either remove the pseudonymised data or anonymise them.

3.3.2 Data breaches

Under the GDPR, when a data breach results to exposure of a data subject's personal data, the data controller needs to notify the supervisory authority no later than 72 hours after the breach occurred (or give reasonable justification in case more time is needed). Quoting from the GDPR, the notification needs to:

1. *describe the nature of the personal data breach including where possible, the categories and approximate number of data subjects concerned and the categories and approximate number of personal data records concerned;*
2. *communicate the name and contact details of the data protection officer or other contact point where more information can be obtained;*
3. *describe the likely consequences of the personal data breach;*
4. *describe the measures taken or proposed to be taken by the controller to address the personal data breach, including, where appropriate, measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects.*

When the above data cannot be collected at the same time, partial information may be given without delay as missing information is collected.

ChildRescue shall incorporate and implement all best practices regarding safe registration, authentication, authorisation and data storage. Databases will be audited and monitored so that the details of every access are logged. In the case of a data breach, mitigation measures will be carried out, depending on the extent and nature of the breach. In the case that the breach occurs in anonymised and/or pseudonymised data, access to the offending addresses will be blocked, whereas in case that a data breach occurs in raw data (e.g. pseudonymised data plus the database that contain the re-identification data), databases will be quarantined, and access will be restricted only to trustworthy parties. In all cases, the supervisory authority will be notified with all the information required by the GDPR. In the case of SoC and Hellenic Red Cross, the supervisory authority is the

Hellenic Data Protection Authority (DPA)². In the case of Child Focus, the supervisory authority is the Commission de la protection de la vie privée³.

3.3.3 Right of access and right to be forgotten

The GDPR dictates that before any processing of a data subject's data takes place, the data subject must give her/his permission. Moreover, the data subject shall be aware at any time of whether her/his data are being used for procession. If personal data are indeed being processed, the data subject must be able to know the purposes of the processing, the exact kind of data that are being processed, the parties to which the results of the processing will be disclosed and whether the data is used in any automated decision-making. In any case, the data subject will be able to revoke permission to the controller to perform any processing on her/his data and even to delete any personal information already stored.

In the case of ChildRescue data subjects can be distinguished in two categories. The first category concerns individuals like missing children or parents of unaccompanied minors which are part of the stakeholder's group of ChildRescue. The second category consists of registered users to the ChildRescue platform.

Concerning stakeholder's personal data, these are absolutely needed only as long as the case is open. Often, as is the case with an Amber Alert, these data are released publicly and, in this sense, cannot be practically deleted since they have already been disseminated to the entire world. In any case, ChildRescue will delete any sensitive information that is stored locally in mobile devices and will remove sensitive information from any part of the platform that is displayed publicly, once the case is over. Users will also be notified that they should delete any data that they, by their own actions, have stored, such as phone screenshots containing the child's face. The users will be notified both via an application notification and via an e-mail (in case they do not longer use the application) that they are required to delete any relevant data that they may have stored. In case however, a user stops using the application and has, without updating her/his profile, altered her/his communication detail there will be impossible to contact this user. Under this circumstance, Article 19 of the GDPR applies, which covers cases when contacting the holder of the data is impossible or requires a disproportionate effort. It is to be noted that the above applies to data that are shared publicly. The subject's data that are stored in the organisation's premises follow a different policy. This happens because these data contain part of the cases both ongoing and closed. For ongoing cases the reason for keeping data is obvious; however even in close cases the data may be needed again. This can happen when a similar case is opened (e.g. the same child disappears again), or if a legal authority (e.g. the Police or District Attorney) requires for data from past cases for some legal reason (e.g. to press charges on a person that is suspect of being part of an abduction network that had a part to some of the past cases). Thus, stakeholder data that are part of past and ongoing cases, are never deleted. The same applies to stakeholder data that were never intended to be disseminated publicly, such as unaccompanied minors. In this case, the personal data remain solely within the data controller, which in ChildRescue consists of SoC, Hellenic Red Cross and Child Focus and are similarly kept for an indefinite amount of time.

² <http://www.dpa.gr/>

³ <http://www.privacycommission.be/>

Regardless of the extent to which stakeholder's personal data have been disseminated to the public, ChildRescue will provide the right of access and erasure by performing anonymisation on undisclosed personal data. In case the stakeholder expresses her/his desire to revoke access and/or erase the data, the already stored pseudonymised data will be converted to anonymised data by moving the relevant entries from the pseudonymised data set to the anonymised data set.

3.3.4 User Identification

When authorities examine whether to disclose children's personal data to the public, they weight in the pros and cons and decide to the best interest of the child. There is always the danger that disclosed information may be used with malicious intent; this danger however may be deemed acceptable depending on the case. As ChildRescue will be used to broadcast information concerning ongoing cases of missing children, the same danger also lurks; namely that ChildRescue will be used by abusers to locate missing children.

ChildRescue supports two kinds of registration, anonymous and named. In anonymous registration, the user will receive the public notification of the authorities, like public alerts and will of course be able to contact the authorities in case of a finding; however, she/he will not be able to participate in the investigation via ChildRescue by providing evidence to the platform. In that sense, ChildRescue will not provide to anonymous users any more information than that already given to the general public and already deemed acceptable by the authorities.

For named registration, ChildRescue will require that users will undergo an identification procedure which will require from them to prove their identity before being able to use the platform. Section 3.2.4 describes how "Know Your Customer" techniques can be employed to identify the physical identity of users online. ChildRescue will use such an infrastructure and will store permanently the relevant data in case they will be required by the authorities. This circumvention of the "Right to be forgotten" of the GDPR is justified under Article 23 and will clearly be stated to the User before using the platform.

3.3.5 Consent

Storing and processing any kind of personal data requires the explicit consent of a data subject. It is therefore necessary to provide to each user a consent form written in clear language that definitely describes both the kind of personal data that are going to be collected and the purposes of data processing. Since the exact kind of information collected and processed may depend on the profiling and decision-making algorithms that are going to be developed in the context of ChildRescue, it is not possible at this moment to define exactly the kind of data that the consent form will cover. However, the consent form will clearly indicate:

- The identity of the data controllers and data processor. In the case of ChildRescue, controllers and processors coincide and consist of SoC, Hellenic Red Cross and Child Focus. In case an organisation wishes to use a third party for processing after commercialisation of ChildRescue, the consent form will be updated accordingly.
- The kind of personal data that will be collected from each data subject.
- Which of the data are going to be used for profiling, decision-making and statistical analysis purposes and in what way.
- Clear indication that the data subject can ask and be granted permission to view what kind of personal information is stored at any time.

- Clear indication that the data subject may at any time revoke her/his consent and that after revocation, their personal data will be removed from the platform within a reasonable time. This only concerns data that do not constitute legal evidence; the case for legal evidence data is considered in the next paragraph.
- Clear indication that in case ChildRescue makes any change to the described way that personal data are handled, the subject will be notified and consent will be asked again.

The above GDPR requirements are typical with any application that uses personal data; ChildRescue however is not typical in the sense that data subjects are part of an official police investigation. Not only may it be required that the police contact them directly, their data may also constitute legal evidence and as such may not be completely removed. This exception will also be stated in the Consent form and the exact kind of data that will be exempt from their right of erasure will also be clearly stated.

It must be noted that consent covers mainly the users of the platform, whether these are anonymous citizens or registered users. Subjects of ChildRescue however include also missing children, for which an Amber Alert has been issued, and unaccompanied minors.

Missing children cannot of course give consent for storing, or even publishing personal data. These cases follow a different procedure with consent being given by the appropriate authorities like the District Attorney or by setting a legal basis like the “protection of the vital interests of the data subject” (GDPR art, 6.1.d). ChildRescue will only disseminate Subject’s information that is already present in the Amber Alert and have thus been already been made publicly available by the Authorities. Though consent is not given explicitly to ChildRescue to also store or disseminate this information, doing so will facilitate the citizens to act as social sensors thereby improving the chances of locating the child. As long as this processing increases the chances of finding the child, consent may not be explicitly asked to process the subject’s data. This is covered by Article 6.1.d as well as recital 46 of the GDPR. In order to better safeguard the interests of the missing child, additional information may be protected. For example, the last name of the child is seldom used when locating a child; in the vast majority of the cases the child is recognised by the picture. Thus, the last name of the child may be omitted by the notification pushed by the ChildRescue Platform.

Unaccompanied minors on the other hand need to register in shelters, where they also provide consent for the usage of their data by the corresponding Legal Entity that is responsible for their sheltering (e.g. Hellenic RED CROSS). ChildRescue needs to collect these data too, in order to be able to perform predictions regarding the possible location or route of an unaccompanied minor, in case she/he has disappeared. The data needed are exactly the same as that, that the original consent form already contains. However, explicit consent must be given to ChildRescue to also use these data. Therefore, a copy of the consent form, applied to ChildRescue Platform, will also be given to the subjects.

For the users of the ChildRescue Platform, a sample Consent Form can be found in Annex II – Sample Consent Form.

4 Privacy and anonymisation in ChildRescue

In the present Section a detailed description will be given of how the techniques of pseudonymisation, pseudonyms and encryption are going to be used in the context of ChildRescue to ensure data privacy and GDPR compliance. Though Section 2 has presented the main approach that is to be followed, the present Section focuses more on technical aspects, outlining the architecture that the modules will implement to provide the required functionalities.

Figure 10 depicts a level 0 data flow diagram of the components responsible implementing the pseudonymisation/anonymisation and encryption policies of ChildRescue. Components in blue boxes correspond to components of the security infrastructure and typically operate as interfaces between users and the ChildRescue Platform. Components in green correspond to ChildRescue components on which security policies are enforced for accessing/using them, but are not in other way part of the security infrastructure. Arrows annotated with a key correspond to encrypted communication. A platform user will be able to login either anonymously or eponymously using secure/encrypted channels. If she/he wishes to register eponymously, she/he will register via a KYC Infrastructure. If she/he requires a pseudonym, this process will be facilitated via the Pseudonym Module which will act as an intermediary in the registration process. The User will be required to accept a consent form; if she/he does, the pseudonymisation/anonymisation module will store her/his data by performing pseudonymisation whereas if, at any point, the consent is revoked, the same module will convert the user's pseudonymised data to anonymised.

Case Data are handled by the organisations that use ChildRescue and may be integrated into ChildRescue, or be stored externally. In any case, evidence that are provided by the User constitute part of this case data and therefore need to be transmitted encrypted. The case data are also pseudonymised by the pseudonymisation /anonymisation; anonymisation in this case happens when the case is closed.

Figure 10: High level data flow for the Anonymisation/Encryption Infrastructure

The next sections describe the architecture and technologies which are going to be used for each of the modules. KYC, which is based on image recognition is a special case; it was described in general in Section 3.2.4. Since its implementation involve mainly image recognition technologies which are not

specific to security, its detailed architecture will be given in D3.1 "ChildRescue Architecture and Platform Design".

4.1 Pseudonymisation and anonymisation

As already mentioned, pseudonymisation and anonymisation refer to any technique that obfuscates or encrypts data with the process of pseudonymisation being reversible, while that of anonymisation being irreversible. Both techniques can, and will in the context of ChildRescue, employ encryption to perform the required transformation; the encryption infrastructure will be described in section 4.3, here we only present the process by which anonymisation is performed.

The overall architecture of the module performing pseudonymisation and anonymisation is depicted in Figure 11. The module includes the following components:

Consent database: A database which stores the data subjects who have provided consent to the ChildRescue platform.

Framework database: A database which contains the PIIs of all the data subjects whose data disclosure is covered by the Regulatory Framework of D1.2.

Re-identification database: A database which contains the original data of the data subjects or other data which can be used to match the pseudonymised (or anonymised) data to the data subjects. These data need to be pseudonymised (or anonymised) and their access is restricted only to the authorised personnel.

Exposed database: A database which contains the pseudonymised data which are accessed and disseminated to the various parties which use the ChildRescue platform.

Pseudonymisation: A component that will perform pseudonymisation transformations on the data

Anonymisation: A component that will anonymise the data

Data adapter: A software component which is responsible to implement the pseudonymisation of the data.

The pseudonymisation process is briefly described below:

When collecting personal data, the Data Adapter will query the Consent database and the Framework database. The consent database will have stored a map of all subjects that have provided consent to the ChildRescue platform. As mentioned above, the Framework database will contain the PIIs of all data subjects whose personal data disclosure is covered by the Regulatory Framework as it is described in D1.2 (e.g. a child for which a distinct attorney has provided permission to issue an amber alert). If confirmation from the consent or the framework database occurs, the Pseudonymisation Module will perform pseudonymisation on the data; it will store the pseudonymised data in an open dataset that can generally be accessed by parties being in communication with ChildRescue and will store the re-identification data in a separate database; the Re-identification database. The Re-identification database will not be publicly accessed but will be used and maintained by each of the data controller's explicitly trained personnel. When re-identification is needed at run-time (e.g. when the e-mail of a user needs to be verified), the Pseudonymisation Module will communicate with the Re-identification database to obtain the original data; apart from this case, access to the re-identification database will be restricted.

After storage, an extra *Anonymisation* module will provide the functionality of generating anonymised data from the exposed data set. It will be based on the **ARX Framework**⁴ and will produce a data set with high *k-value*, *l-diversity* and *t-closeness* parameters. In case the platform operator imports a population table, the *Anonymisation* module will also produce a low value of δ (for the specifics of *k-value*, *l-diversity*, *t-closeness* and δ -difference, please consult Section 3.2.1.1). The anonymised data set will contain all useful information regarding user actions and cases and can still be used to compute analytics and provide useful feedback. Since data subjects cannot be de-identified from the anonymised data set, it can be stored or archived regardless of the status of consent forms.

In case that a subject is removed from the framework database or a consent is revoked, the Pseudonymisation Module will remove for this subject the re-identification data form the re-identification database. The pseudonymised data will be automatically converted to anonymous data upon this removal, so they can still be stored in the Exposed database. Upon revocation of consent, the deletion of re-identification data may take some time due to the system having to poll the consent database and the technical expert receiving the notification to delete re-identification data. This will be explicitly noted in the consent form.

Figure 11: Architecture of the Pseudonymisation module

The pseudonymisation module will perform a combination of techniques as these were documented in Section 2. The administrator of the platform will be able to define which transformations are needed to ensure proper pseudonymisation or anonymisation.

The set of transformation offered will consist of both one-way hashes⁵ and two-way encryption (possibility to encrypt and decrypt the data) as well as all the data masking techniques, except from shuffling. The reason that shuffling is being excluded, is because it couples data of multiple subjects.

⁴ <https://arx.deidentifier.org/>

⁵ A one-way hash function, also known as a message digest, fingerprint or compression function, is a mathematical function which takes a variable-length input string and converts it into a fixed-length binary sequence. Furthermore, a one-way hash function is designed in such a way that it is hard to reverse the process, that is, to find a string that hashes to a given value (hence the name one-way.)

If one subject revokes consent, it is difficult to undo the transformation without affecting data corresponding to other subjects.

Table 4-1 shows some sample transformations that will take place in the context of ChildRescue. By definition, reversible transformation leads to pseudonymised data, while irreversible leads to anonymised data. As noted, the module will be configurable by the platform administration regarding which transformations to perform on which fields. Typically, fields that contain personal data, that are however useful for the operation of the system (e.g. e-mail addresses) will be encrypted, with the decryption key stored in the re-identification database. Non-operational personal data will be data masked with the optional possibility to perform encryption upon the masked data. As previously stated, anonymising the data will be performed by erasing the relevant information for the re-identification database, these being the encryption key in case of encryption and the transformation entry from the transformation matrix in the case of data masking.

Table 4-1: Pseudonymisation techniques offered by ChildRescue

Technique	Type of output	Reversible/irreversible	GDPR Compliance
Nulling	Empty	Irreversible	Yes
Substitution	Plain	Reversible	As long as consent is given
Text Masking	Plain	Irreversible	Yes
Image Masking	Picture	Irreversible	Yes
Hashing	Cipher	Irreversible	Yes
Encryption	Cipher	Reversible	As long as consent is given
Variance	Plain	Reversible	Not by its own
Pruning	Empty	Irreversible	Yes

4.2 Pseudonyms

Pseudonyms in ChildRescue will be used to provide to the registered users the option to appear with a realistic pseudonym in the platform. Under the present process, a citizen may provide anonymous information without disclosing any personal information, not even to the call center operators. This will continue to apply in ChildRescue by allowing anonymous registration. Pseudonyms will be used in the case where the organisation and the authorities need to be able to discern the identity of the user, but the rest of the community that uses ChildRescue must not. An example of such a case is a citizen who has registered to the platform and wishes to provide evidence for an ongoing case, but feels that the knowledge that she/he provided evidence for, may endanger her/him or the case's subject. In order to obfuscate her/his identity in evidence viewed by the ChildRescue community, the identity of the citizen may be substituted by a pseudonym that is negotiated between her/him and the ChildRescue platform.

The architecture for the pseudonym generation module, as this will be implemented in ChildRescue, is depicted in Figure 12. The main components that are used during the process are described below:

Pseudonym client: A s/w component which provides an interface to the end user in order to support the pseudonym generation process.

Negotiator: The negotiator component is used to agree with the user upon a key that will be used for encryption of the communication throughout the pseudonym generation process.

Pseudonym Generator: The pseudonym generator generates the pseudonym under which the user will appear.

Pseudo certificate creator: The pseudo certificate creator generates the certificate which will be used by the user throughout future communications. The pseudo certificate certifies the pseudo-user; that means the user under the pseudonym.

Identity Management Proxy: A component responsible for delegating the traffic data to the logging and auditing module. The component also verifies that the pseudo user corresponds to the actual user for which the pseudo-certificate was issued.

The pseudonym generation process is as follows: A user at first accesses the Pseudonym client. The Pseudonym client is connected to the Negotiator via a Web Anonymisation infrastructure [5] which hides the IP of the user and allows her/him to connect anonymously. The user agrees upon a symmetric key⁶ with the negotiator which is transmitted back to her/him. The user can then use this key to communicate securely with the Pseudonym generation module to create a pseudo certificate. The pseudo certificate data and the corresponding re-identification meta-data are stored in the module's internal storage. The user can then communicate via a 2-way SSL⁷ Channel with the platform by using the pseudo-certificate. The traffic is proxied by the responsible Identity Management Proxy. The logging and auditing module logs the traffic for auditing purposes and it further delegates the traffic data to the authorisation module which confirms the validity of the pseudo-certificate and responds back to the user by using the reverse process.

Figure 12: Pseudonym generation module architecture

⁶ Symmetric-key algorithms are algorithms for cryptography that use the same cryptographic keys for both encryption of plaintext and decryption of ciphertext. The keys may be identical or there may be a simple transformation to go between the two keys.

⁷Two-way SSL or Mutual authentication refers to two parties authenticating each other through verifying the provided digital certificate so that both parties are assured of the others' identity. In technology terms, it refers to a client (web browser or client application) authenticating themselves to a server (website or server application) and that server also authenticating itself to the client through verifying the public key certificate/digital certificate issued by the trusted Certificate Authorities (CAs)

4.3 Encryption

Encryption in ChildRescue will be performed both in the level of communication and in the level of storage, where it is needed.

For the purposes of communication, ChildRescue will use a typical Public Key Infrastructure⁸ that will ensure that certificates shared between parties are trusted and will apply common cryptographic protocols to ensure that data are transmitted securely. The specifications of how a typical PKI is setup was given in Section 3.2.3; ChildRescue will use this setup. Since most of the traffic will be over the Web, the ChildRescue platform will be deployed under the HTTPS platform and appropriately verified certificates will be distributed to all client applications that need to connect.

Encryption will also be performed for ensuring that proper authorisation and authentication is performed for each user, without the danger of account hijacking. This encryption will take place on top of the usual traffic encryption and will ensure that no information regarding user password credentials is stored unencrypted. Since authentication of a user requires that the hash of the given password matches the hash of the stored password, no decryption is needed. A one-way encryption scheme for user passwords will thus be used.

As was also explained in Section 4.1, encryption will also be used when storing certain data. Data for which anonymisation is required from the start, will be encrypted using a one-way algorithm, namely the Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA). Pseudonymised data on the other hand will be stored by using a public key algorithm, namely the RSA. Since the key pair in the case of RSA is only needed for re-identification, this will be exclusively stored in the ChildRescue Platform, and when data expire it will be deleted. The procedure is depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Encryption for data fields.

⁸ A Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) is a set of roles, policies, and procedures needed to create, manage, distribute, use, store, and revoke digital certificates and manage public-key encryption. The purpose of a PKI is to facilitate the secure electronic transfer of information for a range of network activities such as e-commerce, internet banking and confidential email.

5 Conclusions

In the present document the technical details of the encryption and anonymisation techniques that are going to be used in ChildRescue were presented. The algorithms and modules to be implemented are in line with the technical requirements that derive from the need for GDPR conformity. Since these modules will be used at any time when personal data is going to be stored, communicated and processed, ChildRescue will be GDPR compliant concerning data privacy requirements.

Apart from pseudonymisation and anonymisation techniques, ChildRescue will also implement consent monitoring functionalities that will lead to data erasure upon consent revocation. This process will offer ChildRescue the provision of the required data control to data subjects.

Annex I - References

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- [4] Data Cube: A Relational Aggregation Operator Generalizing Group-By, Cross-Tab, and Sub-Totals, Jim Gray, Surajit Chaudhuri, Adam Bosworth, Andrew Layman, Don Reichart, Murali Venkatrao, Frank Pellow, Hamid Pirahesh, January 1997, *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery: Volume 1 Issue 1*, 1997
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- [7] Machanavajjhala, Ashwin; Kifer, Daniel; Gehrke, Johannes; Venkatasubramanian, Muthuramakrishnan (March 2007). "L-diversity: Privacy Beyond K-anonymity". *ACM Trans. Knowl. Discov. Data.*
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Annex II – Sample Consent Form

We provide a sample Consent Form that users will have to accept before using ChildRescue. Many of the details of this form may be modified through the project, however the sample contains all the basic Sections that inform the Users regarding their rights and obligations when using ChildRescue. *ChildRescue Entity* refers to any organisation that deploys and uses ChildRescue for its operations. The list consists of SoC, Hellenic Red Cross and ChildFocus, but may include any sanctioned organism in the future. In this sense, the term *ChildRescue Entity* that appears in the sample consent form is meant to be replaced by the name of each organisation which uses ChildRescue and needs to distribute the consent form.

The *ChildRescue Entity*, identified as *We*, with which *You*, enters in agreement when using *ChildRescue*, processes Personal Data both as a Controller as defined in the and the EU Data Protection Directive GDPR.

Data Collected

You can use *ChildRescue* either anonymously or by registration. In both cases, and to ensure the correct operation of the ChildRescue platform, *ChildRescue* will collect data regarding Your:

- Location
- Network

When You register, you will be able to be more actively take part to ongoing missing children investigations. For this reason, a verification of Your identity must take place before disclosing to You data regarding ongoing investigation. The registration and identification procedure will collect data regarding Your:

- Identification number
- Name
- Date of birth
- Sex
- Age
- Eye colour
- Hair colour
- Marital Status

ChildRescue will also ask You to prove your identity in case You register.

Usage of Your Data by the Authorities

We inform You that when using *ChildRescue*, you will become a member of official investigation by providing feedback to ongoing missing children cases. As such you agree that:

- The authorities can use Your data to come into contact with You, if the need arises.
- Data collected by Us, and which are relevant to an ongoing investigation may be handled to the authorities if requested.
- When You give feedback to an ongoing investigation that is officially carried out by the Police. Since feedback given by You can be used for present or future legal

investigations, Your identification number, feedback and locations from every feedback You have given will be not deleted from Our databases even if You request so. Please refer to Article 23 of the GDPR.

Usage of Your Data by the Third Parties

We inform you that we may share Your data with other Humanitarian Organisations dealing with missing children so that to increase the efficiency of cross border investigations. Data will be shared in the same format as stored in our databases so that the same mechanisms of archiving and deletion can be applied to them by the third party entities. We will ensure that the third party:

- Is based on a country that has adopted GDPR
- Is explicitly required by contract that it will enforce our data policy regarding Your personal data
- In case that You revoke Your consent, it will be notified within 2 working days regarding Your revocation and will be required to delete all of Your data form its premises within 5 working days after notification has been sent.

Your rights concerning your data

ChildRescue performs pseudonymisation and anonymisation on Your personal data as these are recommended by the GDPR. What this means is that:

- Your personal data are stored in a way that is unreadable except from the *ChildRescue Entity* technical personnel and the ChildRescue Application.
- The above process is implemented by following best practices in encryption and anonymisation to ensure that the data are securely stored
- Special data that can lead to the re-identification of Your personal data, are kept in separate database, which is referred to as the *Identification Database*, and can only be accessed by the *ChildRescue Entity* technical personnel.

You have the right to:

- At any time request and retrieve information regarding how Your data are used and/or processed.
- Rectification of Your personal data in case You find inaccuracies and/or omissions.
- Erasure of Your data that are already being stored. Upon request, Your identification entries will be removed within 24 hours upon receipt of request from the *Identification Database* and You will not be able to identified by the platform or by any *ChildRescue* operator any more. An exception is that of your identification number, feedback You provided and the locations from which You provided it as this is justified in Section Usage of Your Data by the Authorities. You can request that these Personal Data become *offline*, meaning that they will be stored in facilities without network access.
- Restrict the processing of your data. This right involves only Us; if authorities need Your data for processing, the *ChildRescue Entity* will provide the data.
- Download all your stored data in portable formats

Please note that any processing, profiling and decision making performed by ChildRescue, will generate suggestions that will have impact on ongoing investigations. You will not be the subject of any such process.

Why We process Your data

Collection and processing of Your data is necessary for *ChildRescue Entity* to perform its tasks that are necessary for the public interest. More specifically, collection of Your data is necessary for registering and/or identifying you when You use ChildRescue to view alerts and/or provide evidence (see also the *Data Collected Section*). Procession of Your data is needed to perform analytics on past and current cases; these analytics will provide prognostic functionality to the Entity and they will aid the Entity to future cases. In case You register with identification, Your personal data will also be processed in order to match You against the evidence You provided in order to evaluate Your reliability. Your personal data will be stored to the Entities' storage infrastructure. The Entity may share Your personal data with the authorities upon a legal request (please refer to the *Usage of Your Data by the Authorities Section*). For the process of deleting Your personal data upon Your request, please refer to *Your rights concerning Your data Section*. In any case, Your Personal Data will be anonymised, after 5 years of inactivity. Anonymisation means that the Entity will have no way of identifying You from the platform's data. The Entity however will still keep a minimum of Your Personal information; please refer to Section *Usage of Your Data by the Authorities*.

Cookie details

We inform You, that ChildRescue uses essential cookies for maintaining session information, performance cookies that collect non-identifiable user experience information and functional cookies to store Your personal preferences. The list of cookies that we use can be found in the following table:

Your obligations concerning the data of the ChildRescue application

- You are not allowed to keep any copy of the data of the closed cases. Any records related to the data or copy of the data of a case that You by Your own have exported in any format, should, also, be destroyed as soon as the case is closed and removed from the ChildRescue application.

[TABLE OF COOKIES SAMPLE ROW]

Provider	Name	Type	Expiration	Purpose
ChildRescue	Session_id	Session information	5 days	Maintain information that keeps Your session valid through transactions with the platformm

Contact Details

For any feedback you can contact us at:

[CHILDRESUCE ENTITY ADDRESS DETAILS]

The *ChildRescue Entity* has a Data Protection Officer who is responsible for issues relating to privacy and data protection. You can reach the Data Protection Officer at:

[DATA PROTECTION OFFICER ADDRESS DETAILS]

Annex III – Ethics Advisory Board report for D2.3

The current section provides the outcomes and the conclusions that derived from the Ethics Advisory Board teleconference.

The ChildRescue Ethics Advisory Board D2.3 Teleconference

Table Annex III-1: The ChildRescue Ethics Advisory Board (names and position).

Name	Position
Philip Ishola (EAB Chair) (PI)	LOVE-146 international in human rights and technology
Karen Shalev Greene (KSG)	Director of the Centre for the Study of Missing Persons
Eva Lievens (EL)	Professor Specialised in Human rights and technology
Spiros Salamastrakis (SS)	Lawyer
Prof. Dr. Andreas Jud	Professor
Peter Van Dyck (PVD)	Lawyer
Thanasis Giannetsos	Lecturer in Secure Systems
Antoine Bon (AB)	Legal advisor

The Board was sent, before the meeting, some relevant questions, that they answered during the teleconference. The meeting took place on Wednesday 12th of September 2018, at 14.00 to 16.00 CEST. Members of the Board that were attending are: Karen Shalev Greene, Eva Lievens, Spiros Salamastrakis, Peter Van Dyck, and Antoine Bon. From NTUA, the meeting was hosted by Christos Ntanos (CN), Ariadni Michalitsi, Eleni Kanellou, and Dimitris Varoutas who kept the minutes and took notes during the meeting. Isabelle Brantl from FRA-UAS, Dimitris Ntalaperas (DN), and Danae Vergeti from UBITECH also attended the teleconference. The members of the Board that were unable to attend the meeting will provide us with their written remarks.

In this report the meeting minutes, the issues that were discussed, additional comments from EAB members after the teleconference, a table with the ethics requirements list along with the EAB conclusions, and an annex with the questions that were prepared for the EAB members are given.

Meeting minutes

In this section the meeting minutes are quoted.

Requirement No. 2

CN read the prepared question related to the fulfilment of requirement No2. (all the prepared questions can be found in the Annex of this report).

KSG expressed the opinion that the part explaining the reasons why ChildRescue processes the acquired data is very generic. In her opinion, the written part in the deliverable doesn't describe in detail what ChildRescue intends to do with the data. She suggested that a couple of sentences need to be added in the consent form. Namely she suggested: what is the point of processing the data, which is the target end of this process, how the information will be stored and how, and when it will be destroyed.

AB agreed with KSG. Specifically, he made a mention to the identification number. In some countries there are specific rules about identification number. He also wondered why ChildRescue collects some information such as eye colour, sex, age, hair colour and marital status.

CN answered that the purpose of the collection of that information has to do with the profiling of the data subjects which are the missing children. ChildRescue will collect at least the same information that NGOs under the umbrella of MCE collect already in similar operations. For anonymous accounts, the consent refers either to children that are not missing e.g. unaccompanied migrant minors (UMM) and/or the families of the victims of disappearances.

AB thinks that ChildRescue has an issue considering article 23 of GDPR which restricts the data subjects' rights e.g. right to be forgotten. ChildRescue needs a legal basis to do that.

DN answered that citizens may be part of the investigation. He said that ChildRescue needs to keep some basic data about the investigation in case the police or the district attorney needs them later. ChildRescue does not have to delete all the data regarding the case.

PVD said that it seems to be a number of types of information that are not included that in the consent form, that is required to be given (article 13 GDPR). ChildRescue needs to be clear of the recipients that it could send the data.

DN said that there are two kinds of data. The first kind comes from the registered users whom ChildRescue initially has to verify. The other kind of data ChildRescue will keep, depends on the algorithms that will be used. Regarding the second kind of data, ChildRescue does not have a defined list. It will be defined in the second iteration. In any case, the consent form will contain all these data and it will state why it will be stored, and which of the data, the data subject does not have the right to ask to be deleted.

PVD said that ChildRescue has to specify the manner that data will be processed and inform the data subjects on which legal basis the provided data will be used. ChildRescue needs to also mention in the consent form, that the person filling in the form has the right to withdraw their consent. ChildRescue also needs to inform that it may share the information with specific authorities or companies. There is certain required information that is missing at the moment.

AB added that article 13 GDPR obliges us to inform users about the exact description of the recipients of those data, not precisely provide the names of them but a concise description, for instance, humanitarian associations associated with the platform.

CN added that the categories could be e.g. missing children organisations under the umbrella of MCE and organisations that handle shelters for UMM.

AB said that it would be better to describe more precisely when ChildRescue is a processor and when it is a controller of the data. He specified that processor is the entity or individual that process data on behalf of someone else and that controller is the entity or individual that process data for their own use.

DN said that ChildRescue may omit the processor part if it makes the issue simpler, as the cases which the processing will be taking place for someone else is scarce.

Requirement No. 3

CN read the prepared question related to the fulfilment of requirement No3.

PVD thinks that it is not enough to get the consent from the district attorney instead of directly the child. This can only be the case if there are legal grounds such as public interest. If ChildRescue wants to rely on consent at such a ground, he wondered if this would be enough.

CN said that this procedure already takes place in missing children organisations. They have the right to collect and process similar information. The data collection already begins when there is a call to the missing children organisations to declare a missing child. They are given the right to collect data. The organisations gather data both from the parents and from the police. There is a consent form that the parents fill in when they share information, but due to the hastiness of the investigations, the signing of this consent form is done later.

AB thinks that it is not right to use consent as a legal basis from someone who cannot provide consent. ChildRescue could consider another legal basis (article 6.1.d GDPR). It can be used when another legal basis cannot apply. For example, it can be used (recital 46) in case of humanitarian urgency. This could be an appropriate legal basis.

CN wondered if ChildRescue can do this and if the organisations already deal with this.

Requirement No. 4

CN read the prepared question related to the fulfilment of requirement No4.

CN asked if the Board has even seen a specific mention of stigmatisation or vulnerability in the consent form or any other documentation.

KSG said that people suffered by dementia have reduced consent.

CN said that ChildRescue tries to track UMM, only by the formal registration of the UMM in the shelters. The only information ChildRescue gets, is when they register in the shelters, where they could sign the consent forms for the collection of data both for registering in the shelters (which already happens) as well for ChildRescue. In the case of UMM, ChildRescue will collect the same information that is used in their registration in the shelters. ChildRescue could predict a possible path depending on the information they give. The tracking actually takes place if the UMM appear in another shelter or if they are declared missing. He asked if this is considered as some kind of tracking.

KSG replied that it is not considered as tracking if ChildRescue will use the already given information.

CN said that concerning UMM, there is not any dissemination material. In the case of missing children there is dissemination material, which will contain the same kind of data like the Amber Alert, but it will be directed to the end users of ChildRescue platform (social sensors). The users won't know the geographic area that the notifications are sent. He asked if this would require any kind of different authorisation by the fact that the notifications are sent to the mobile phones' users in the area of the disappearance.

KSG replied that it is fine. As long as ChildRescue can take this information back and there will not be any digital footprints, ChildRescue is fine.

CN said that in ChildRescue, the notifications will be securely deleted from any device that were sent after they are not needed. Of course, the possibility of someone keeping a screenshot cannot be avoided.

KSG noted that in current Amber Alert notifications the full name is shown. She suggested that ChildRescue could show only the first name and not the full name to protect the child. She also

mentioned that studies have also indicated that people rarely recall the last name, but mainly the picture and the first name.

Requirement No. 7

CN read the prepared question related to the fulfilment of requirement No7.

AB mentioned (article 17.2 and article 19 of the GDPR) that if ChildRescue makes the data public, and the data subjects want to exercise their right to be forgotten or other rights, ChildRescue must inform the recipients to whom ChildRescue has sent the data, in order they delete the data too. The only exemption to that is when this is impossible or it requires disproportionate effort. ChildRescue should be ready to explain why it is impossible to do that.

CN wondered what happens if ChildRescue has already deleted the data.

AB answered that it is not enough. ChildRescue has to inform the other recipients that they should also delete the data.

AB gave an example that certain banks send text messages with the pin code of a credit card and that these messages are automatically erased after a specific time period e.g. 2 days.

CN noted that the notifications that ChildRescue will send, will get deleted when Amber Alert is dropped.

AB said that ChildRescue should refer to article 19 GDPR.

SS added that article 19 GDPR gives a solution. If ChildRescue can prove that it is inevitable or extremely difficult to do this procedure, then ChildRescue won't have any problem.

CN said that ChildRescue should mention that the only possibility that the information remains in the recipients' devices is if the recipients take a screenshot, which cannot be controlled by ChildRescue.

CN said that ChildRescue should check if the full or only the first name will be published on the alerts. Obviously, the rest of the information will be the same as the Amber Alert. The police decide which information is published depending on the case.

Requirement No. 9

CN read the prepared question related to the fulfilment of requirement No9.

PVD said that section 2.3.3 describes more the process of deleting the data or moving the data from pseudonymisation to anonymisation. ChildRescue should focus more on the retention of the data. Specifically, ChildRescue should be clearer about the data retention time period. It should have a good reason why specific data should be kept and which will be the time period of the data retention.

CN asked which time period is considered reasonable about the data retention.

Peter answered that GDPR doesn't give a specific time frame to keep the data, but it mentions that an organisation should keep the data for as long it needs to in order to achieve its purpose. It is important to have a good explanation about how long ChildRescue needs to keep the data.

PVD mentioned that ChildRescue should be more transparent about how long it keeps the data. In section 2.3.3, more information should be added specifically if there is a case of keeping the data after the end of the investigation period and mention about contacting the interested party if the data would become relevant in a future investigation.

CN said that ChildRescue will describe a scenario where information will be kept available and used only if the case reopens.

PVD said that the consent form does not contain a clear indication that the data subject can any time revoke their consent.

CN noted that it will be added in the consent form.

EL said that regarding 2.3.3 it is not clear what ChildRescue is going to do if someone asks for certain data to be erased, and also ChildRescue should be careful about the pseudonymisation and anonymisation.

CN said that pseudonymisation takes place when a case is closed. Anonymisation happens after there is certainty that the case won't be reopened.

DN added that anonymisation is equal to deletion and it happens after ChildRescue is certain that the case won't be reopened.

AB and EL said that ChildRescue needs to be clear towards the people giving the consent that they have the right to have the collected data deleted. Section 2.3.4 and everything that is related to the article 17 GDPR i.e. the right to erasure needs to be finetuned a little bit more.

DN said that he will look at it.

AB said that if the data are already in pseudonymised form, and the data subject asks the deletion of the data, ChildRescue must either delete or anonymise the data.

Requirement No. 10

CN read the prepared question related to the fulfilment of requirement No10.

CN mentioned that requirement No. 10 is a requirement that is not possible to be covered at this project's phase.

Requirement No. 11

CN read the prepared question related to the fulfilment of requirement No11.

CN noted that when users are registered, they don't have the same level of access that volunteers of the organisations that perform the active searches have. However, the registered users will receive more information than the general public. ChildRescue will provide extended information in several layers that start from the anonymous users, to the registered eponymous users, to the validated volunteers, and the members of the administrative team of the NGOs that handle the cases. There are several levels of access. CN asked if the different levels of access covers this requirement.

AB said that it is fine to provide different information depending on the level of identification. He asked how ChildRescue plans to identify the validated users.

CN said that the volunteer organisations will validate them. Either the person provides their own information and their personal data already exist on the organisation's database and a match happens or an invitation could be sent to them by an organisation to join the platform. The rest of the users are on the same level of access as the anonymous users. It should be clarified that on the name registration, the identification procedure refers to the members of the volunteers' teams and the identification happens by the organisations they belong to.

CN reported that maybe two apps may be developed: a lightweight app for the general public and another for the members of the volunteers' organisations and the members of the NGOs handling those cases.

Requirement No. 12

CN read the prepared question related to the fulfilment of requirement No12.

CN said that ChildRescue won't provide more information than it is already disseminated with for instance, Amber Alert, but there is always the possibility of misuse of the platform, like it may happen with an Amber Alert. ChildRescue will follow the common practice.

AB suggested to examine previous cases about abuse of similar platforms and determine what kind of information is appropriate to disseminate.

KSG said that there is limited research about which is the appropriate amount and what is the proper kind of information that should be disseminated.

CN claims that regarding the validity of the sightings, an algorithm will rank the usefulness of these sightings so that it can attribute different weights on the information provided.

General considerations and recommendations about the deliverable

The parts of the deliverable that cover the ethics requirements need to be more accurate and align with the GDPR. Then, CN described the next deliverables. A discussion will take place on the progress report at middle October. A teleconference will also take place on December.

Notes

In this second call with the ethics advisory board, whether the ethics requirements are sufficiently met and properly described in D2.3 was discussed. Initially, the discussion was about the processes of acquiring and storing data. Special mention was given to the consent form, and some modifications of the as is structure consent form were proposed. These modifications will fully align the consent form, that someone signs when providing information, with the GDPR requirements. Then the right of a missing child to delete its case once the case is closed, was also addressed. It is very important to be able to inform the individuals that fill in the consent form that they have the right to withdraw their consent whenever they wish to do so and have the case as a whole deleted when the case is closed. Of course, for the purpose of child rescue there will be not to delete the data but pseudonymise them so that data from past cases could be used in the predictive algorithms, that will assist the current and future cases to be solved. Another issue that was raised is who is to give the consent if the missing child is unable to give it, and if the District Attorney is sufficient to do so, as it is currently done. Furthermore, whether CR is to be a processor or a controller of data, and how important it is to also be a processor as it complicates the situation was mentioned. Another issue that was raised is whether CR believes it is mandatory to also mention the last name of the missing child, as studies show that the public mainly remembers the first name and the picture. Finally, the levels of access in the information that the different types of users have was discussed. The meeting was closed with some reference in future cause of action.

Additional comments from EAB members

AB added that clarification should be made about:

- a) Purposes of processing;
- b) Retention policy (how long the data will be kept);
- c) Legal basis (GDPR, art. 6), if the legal basis chosen is the "legal obligation" of 6.2(c) or "public interest" (e) which precise "legal obligation" or "public interest" is referred to;
- d) Recipients of data;

e) Categories of data.

He suggested several ideas, such as:

- Draw a simple diagram of the data flows which would include the aforementioned information (point 1). The data flows involved in the project are complex, ChildRescue and all stakeholders would benefit from a scheme/diagram which would foster clarity and transparency, and allows to better identify the privacy risks;
- Include the notion of “accountability” (GDPR, art. 5.2) which is absent from the document despite being a foundational principle of the Regulation. Among other issues it should include: the obligation to document the consent received; to document data breaches etc;
- In addition, ChildRescue will most likely need to keep a register of its processing activities (GDPR, art. 30), it would be advisable at this stage to already have a draft of this register even if it needs to be completed at a later stage;
- Provide all the required information to the data subjects when their data are collected (GDPR, art. 13);
- Consider other potential legal basis (GDPR, art. 6) to process the missing children data than to obtain consent from the district attorney. As suggested, explore the public interest (GDPR, 6.2(e)) and vital interest grounds (GDPR, 6.2(d) and Recital 46);
- Define the roles of each actors (GDPR, art. 4(7)(8)). As explained during the call, the role of one actor can vary depending on the purposes for which the data are used;
- Check the different Member states `rules concerning the use of national ID number, more researches should be done about the legal rules pertaining to that issue;
- Ground the use of GDPR, art. 23 on a precise legal basis as this provision can only be used under very strict conditions;
- Clarify throughout the text the distinction between “anonymisation” and “pseudonymisation”. For instance, the statement: “When data expire, or consent is revoked, ChildRescue will provide the functionality to either remove the pseudonymised data or anonymise them” (WP2, point 2.3.2, p. 18) is not compliant. When the data served its purposes or the consent is withdrawn the only thing to do is either delete the data or anonymise them;
- Consider articles GDPR, 17.2 and 19, in case data subjects rights are exercised;
- Take note that the Belgian supervisory Authority became the Belgian Data Protection Authority (WP2, point 2.3.2 p. 18).

EL concurred with AB on all the points that still need clarification in order to achieve accuracy from a legal perspective, and in particular (and as mentioned during the call) regarding the legal basis, the restriction of data subject rights, and the distinction between anonymisation and pseudonymisation.

PI added his comments about the ethics requirements list. He suggested that:

- Regarding Requirement No. 2, the language used to specify, correlates with the specified use of the need for the data collection and the use of the data obtained. The clarification of a recipient’s role will make clear what their function and legal requirements are. This addition will

draw together the project's role, expectations incumbent on recipient's as reflected in the relevant sections (2.2 and 2.3) of D2.3.

- Regarding Requirement No. 3, very strong efforts (reflected on policy and a procedure) would need to be made in order to obtain the consent of a child or of the parent who holds legal parental authority or of their legal guardian or, where the legal framework is structured in this way, of the statutory child protection agency responsible for the care of the child. A humanitarian agency may fall outside this process.
 - In extremis e.g. child protection issue/imminent risk of harm, data may be sought and shared.
 - The threshold for 'public interest' is very broad and different across states. Further thought and discussion and advice within and from the EAB be initiated to look specifically at a mechanism, which is GDPR and protection compliant.
 - The existing Missing children procedure, as detailed in the minutes, is strong, however may not be readily transferrable.
- Regarding Requirement No. 4, the risks of non-compliance should be included (examples to be specified e.g. 'screenshot' with sentence reflecting the list is not exhaustive) with a clear statement, requiring all data should be destroyed following the appropriate secure destruction method. It would be responsibility of ChildRescue to ensure this is clearly stated, however the responsibility to ensure destruction in all the situations outside ChildRescue core data collection, retention and destruction protocols, sits with those partners and or participating organisations who hold the data. This is also related to Requirement No. 7.
- Regarding Requirement No. 9, it is required to have a clear indication that the data subject can any time revoke their consent and that a relevant section will be added in the consent form. The process of what ChildRescue is going to do if someone asks for certain data to be erased, should be simply explained using terminology reflected in 2.2 with an additional chapter added to 2. Landscape analysis in privacy and anonymisation.
- Regarding Requirement No. 11, the process needs to be clearly detailed.

Table

Table Annex III-2: Ethics requirements list and conclusions from the EAB telco

<p>2nd Meeting EAB 12th Sept 2018</p> <p>Related Action:</p> <p>D7.1 to D7.12. Points of review with subsequent adjustment sign off</p>	<p>Related Section: Refer to <i>D2.3_Privacy and Anonymisation Methodological Foundations</i></p>	<p>Conclusions from the 2nd Meeting EAB</p>
<p>D7.1 : GEN - Requirement No. 1 [12]</p>		<p>Not yet finalised</p>

A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted with the financial reports.		
D7.2 : H - Requirement No. 2 [3] 2.3. Templates of the informed consent forms and information sheet must be submitted.	D2.3 section 2.3.5	The reasons why ChildRescue processes the acquired data are very generic. A couple of sentences need to be added in the consent form. ChildRescue needs to be clear of the categories of the recipients that it could send the data. Check the section where ChildRescue is described as a processor and/or controller of the data.
D7.3 : H - Requirement No. 3 [3] 2.5. The applicant must clarify how consent/assent will be ensured in case children and/or adults unable to give informed consent are involved.	D2.3 section 2.3.5	Some members of the EAB thought that it is not enough to get the consent from the district attorney instead of directly the child. This can only be done if there are legal grounds such as public interest, or humanitarian urgency, etc.
D7.4 : H - Requirement No. 4 [3] Details must be provided about the measures taken to prevent the risk of enhancing vulnerability/stigmatisation of individuals/groups.	D2.3 section 2.3.3, 2.3.4, 2.3.1	As long as ChildRescue can take this information back and there will not be any digital footprints, ChildRescue is fine. The notifications will be securely deleted from any device that were sent after they are not needed. Of course, the possibility of someone keeping a screenshot cannot be avoided.
D7.5 : H - Requirement No. 5 [3] 2.8. Details on incidental findings policy must be provided.		Not yet finalised
D7.6 : H - Requirement No. 6 [3] 2.9. Copies of ethics approvals for the research with humans must be submitted.		Not yet finalised
D7.7 : POPD - Requirement No. 7 [3] The applicant must explicitly confirm that the data used are publicly available. In case of data not publicly available, relevant authorisations must be provided.	D2.3 section 2.3.3	ChildRescue must inform the recipients to whom ChildRescue has sent the data, in order they delete the data too. The only exemption to that is when this is impossible or it requires disproportionate effort (article 19 GDPR). ChildRescue should be ready to explain why it is impossible to do that.
D7.8 : POPD - Requirement No. 8 [3] 4.1. Copies of opinion or confirmation by the		Not yet finalised

<p>competent Institutional Data Protection Officer and/or authorisation or notification by the National Data Protection Authority must be submitted (which ever applies according to the Data Protection Directive (EC Directive 95/46, currently under revision, and the national law).</p>		
<p>D7.9 : POPD - Requirement No. 9 [3] Detailed information must be provided on the procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation.</p> <p>The project intends to develop a mobile application. Details on the privacy policy and permissions must be provided (in this case, it is important to make sure that app users are aware that their data will be accessible by police authorities).</p> <p>The app also allows for real-time messaging among police forces and members of the community.</p> <p>In order to avoid wrongful information to be circulated, the dynamics of real-time messaging must be explained. In particular, it must be ensured that all information shared with the community is part of an ongoing investigation and has clearance to be disseminated among the public by a police or judicial body.</p>	<p>D2.3 section 2.3.3 & section 2.3 intro</p> <p>D2.3 Section 2.3.5</p> <p>D2.3 section 2.1, section 2.2.3</p> <p>D2.3 section 2.3.4 and 2.2.2</p> <p>D2.3 section 2.3.3 (last paragraph) and 2.3.1</p>	<p>ChildRescue should have a good reason why specific data should be kept and it should be clearer about the data retention time period.</p> <p>ChildRescue should keep the data for as long it needs to in order to achieve its purpose.</p> <p>ChildRescue will describe a scenario where information will be kept available and used only if the case reopens.</p> <p>A clear indication that the data subject can any time revoke their consent will be added in the consent form.</p> <p>It is not clear what ChildRescue is going to do if someone asks for certain data to be erased. ChildRescue should be careful about the pseudonymisation and anonymisation. Pseudonymisation takes place when a case is closed. Anonymisation is equal to deletion and it happens after ChildRescue is certain that the case won't be reopened.</p>

<p>The applicant has provided draft terms of use of the platform that indicate, for instance, that “You [app user] are solely responsible for your conduct and any data, text, information, screen names, graphics, photos, profiles, audio and video clips, links (“Content”) that you submit, post, and display on the ChildRescue service.” This is unacceptable as all content would need to be reviewed before being shared. The burden of the potential harmful uses of the platform must fall on the developer/owner, not the user (who can be warned, but not be made responsible).</p> <p>The app will allow for users to register anonymously. While their public identity can be anonymous, police forces should always be able to identify who is providing evidence related to an open case. Many countries forbid anonymous police reports, for instance. The legality and ethics of this point must be clarified.</p> <p>Details on robust data deletion mechanisms (including meta data) once a user decided to leave the platform need to be provided.</p>		<p>ChildRescue needs to be clear towards the people giving the consent that they have the right to have the collected data deleted. Section 2.3.4 and everything that is related to the article 17 GDPR i.e. the right to erasure needs to be finetuned a little bit more.</p> <p>If the data are already in pseudonymised form, and the data subject asks the deletion of the data, ChildRescue must either delete or anonymise the data.</p>
<p>D7.10 : POPD - Requirement No. 10 [6] The project intends to develop predictive</p>	<p>Section 2.3.5 D2.3 not yet covered</p>	<p>It is not possible to be covered at this project’s phase.</p>

algorithms. A detailed description of the data these will use and the assumptions they will make need to be independently assessed.		
<p>D7.11: OEI - Requirement No. 11 [3]</p> <p>The project will encourage citizens to contribute to an ongoing investigation, and thus to act as members of the police force. This has led to cases of mob justice or individuals taking matters into their own hands. The steps taken to ensure that those using the app are aware of what their role is, where it begins and where it ends, need to be provided.</p>	D2.3 section 2.3.4 not fully covered	<p>ChildRescue will provide extended information in several layers that start from the anonymous users, to the registered eponymous users, to the validated volunteers, and the members of the administrative team of the NGOs that handle the cases. There will be several levels of access. It is fine to provide different information depending on the level of identification. The volunteer organisations will validate the users through a know your customer procedure.</p>
<p>D7.12: OEI - Requirement No. 12 [3]</p> <p>The app may be misused by people who intend to locate missing children to abuse them. Details on how this will be avoided must be provided.</p>	Section 2.3.4 d2.3	<p>ChildRescue won't provide more information than it is already disseminated with for instance, Amber Alert, but there is always the possibility of misuse of the platform, like it may happen with an Amber Alert. ChildRescue will follow the common practice.</p>

Annex

Requirement No. 2

The templates of the informed consent form and information sheet can be found in D2.3, subsection 2.3.5. and specifically, in the Annex of the report. In the informed consent form, the interested party finds out the kind of data that are going to be collected, how the data will be used, the rights that are associated with the collected data, why the data need to be processed and some details concerning the cookies. Do you think that any more issues should be addressed to through this form or the aforementioned information are sufficient for the ethics requirement number 2?

Requirement No. 3

The assurance of the consent/assent, in case that children or adults are unable to provide any information for themselves, is specified in D2.3, subsection 2.3.5. Mainly in this case the consent will be given by the appropriate authorities like the Distinct Attorney. Do you consider this to be sufficient for requirement no. 3?

Requirement No. 4

The details that will be provided about the measures taken to prevent the risk of enhancing vulnerability/stigmatisation of individuals/groups, are specified in D2.3 section 2.3.3, 2.3.4, 2.3.1. The right for a case to be addressed and the right of a case to be forgotten are specified, along with the

user identification as well as the aforementioned consent. Do you consider that these 3 aspects cover requirement number 4?

Requirement No. 7

The applicant must explicitly confirm that the data used are publicly available. In case of data not publicly available, relevant authorisations must be provided. The aforementioned requirement is addressed in D2.3 section 2.3.3, where regardless of the extent to which stakeholder's personal data have been disseminated to the public, ChildRescue will provide the right of access and erasure by performing pseudonymisation on undisclosed personal data. In case the relevant party wants the data completely deleted, all the entries will be moved from the pseudonymised data set to the anonymised data set. Do you think this practice covers requirement number 7?

Requirement No. 9

Information about the procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation (in alignment with EU legislation) are addressed in D2.3 section 2.3.3 & section 2.3 intro. All the handling of the data are also GDPR compliant.

As for the mobile application and how the privacy policy and the permissions must be provided is addressed in D2.3 Section 2.3.5., where there will be a clear indication that the data subject may at any time revoke her/his consent and that after revocation, their personal data will be removed from the platform within a reasonable time. Also, clear indication that in case ChildRescue makes any change to the described way that personal data are handled, the subject will be notified and consent will be asked again.

The dynamics of real-time messaging must be explained, in order to avoid the circulation of wrongful information. Information on this can be found in D2.3 section 2.1, section 2.2.3. It must be ensured that all information shared with the community is part of an ongoing investigation and has clearance to be disseminated among the public by a police or judicial body.

As for the draft terms of use of the platform that indicate that "You [app user] are solely responsible for your conduct and any data, text, information, screen names, graphics, photos, profiles, audio and video clips, links ("Content") that you submit, post, and display on the ChildRescue service.", a review process will follow any user submission. The burden of the potential harmful uses of the platform must fall on the developer/owner, not the user (who can be warned, but not be made responsible).

As far as the users' anonymous registration and the need of their identification by police forces in case of the provision of an evidence related to an open case, references can be found in sections 2.3.4 and 2.2.2 of D2.3. Specifically, in section 2.3.4, it explicitly highlights that in anonymous registration "the user will receive the public notification of the authorities, like public alerts and will of course be able to contact the authorities in case of a finding; however, she/he will not be able to participate in the investigation via ChildRescue by providing evidence to the platform. In that sense, ChildRescue will not provide to anonymous users any more information than that already given to the general public and already deemed acceptable by the authorities." Furthermore, in section 2.2.2, where the technical description on data pseudonymisation is provided, it is noted that pseudonyms are used when there is a need that a subject appears under a false identity. That is the case when an informant contacts the police and provides his identity that should however remain secret to the public. Do you find these two descriptions adequate to address the requirement of anonymous registration in certain cases along with police forces identification in the same cases?

On the case of robust data deletion mechanisms, including metadata, once a user decides to leave the platform, section 2.3.3 and 2.3.1 of D2.3 provide an answer. In particular, in section 2.3.3 the following quote addresses this issue as follows: "Concerning stakeholder's personal data, these are absolutely needed only as long as the case is open. Often, as is the case with an Amber Alert, these data are released publicly and, in this sense, cannot be practically deleted since they have already been disseminated to the entire world. In other cases, however, as when we are dealing with an unaccompanied minor whose information has not been publicly disclosed, the personal data remain solely within the data controller, which in ChildRescue consists of SoC, Hellenic Red Cross and Child Focus. Regardless of the extent to which stakeholder's personal data have been disseminated to the public, ChildRescue will provide the right of access and erasure by performing pseudonymisation on undisclosed personal data. In case the stakeholder expresses her/his desire to revoke access and/or erase the data, the pseudonymised data will be converted to anonymised data by moving the relevant entries from the pseudonymised data set to the anonymised data set.". Technically, the pseudonymization and anonymisation techniques are explained in the same deliverable and is explicitly stated that when data expire or consent is revoked, ChildRescue will provide the functionality to either remove the pseudonymised data or anonymise them. Is there any issue on that requirement that is not covered by such descriptions?

Requirement No. 10

Requirement No.10 refers to the development of predictive algorithms and the need for a detailed description of the data these will use and the assumption to be made. In section 2.3.5, on the Consent discussion, it is highlighted that "Since the exact kind of information collected and processed may depend on the profiling and decision-making algorithms that are going to be developed in the context of ChildRescue, it is not possible at this moment to define exactly the kind of data that the consent form will cover." Therefore, it is a requirement that is not possible to be covered at this project's phase.

Requirement No. 11

Requirement No.11 refers to the fact that since the project encourages citizens to contribute to an ongoing investigation, it also needs to ensure that the user of the app is aware of his role and its limits, in order to prevent cases of mob justice or individuals taking matters into their own hands. Although not a specific mention on that is made in D2.3, section 2.3.4 specifies the two types of registration that ChildRescue will support, anonymous and named ones, and the particular features and the rights it will grant. As an example, it notes that "In anonymous registration, the user will receive the public notification of the authorities, like public alerts and will of course be able to contact the authorities in case of a finding; however, she/he will not be able to participate in the investigation via ChildRescue by providing evidence to the platform. In that sense, ChildRescue will not provide to anonymous users any more information than that already given to the general public and already deemed acceptable by the authorities.

For named registration, ChildRescue will require that users will undergo an identification procedure which will require from them to prove their identity before being able to use the platform." Do you believe that a more explicit mention on the ways to ensure that an app user will not cross his role's limits should be made at ChildRescue's deliverables?

Requirement No. 12

Requirement no.12 refers to the risk of misuse of the app by people who intend to locate missing children to abuse them. Details on how this will be avoided must be provided. All section 2.3.4 of D2.3

answers on that problem referring to the issue of user identification. Specifically, it is noted that “There is always the danger that disclosed information may be used with malicious intent; this danger however may be deemed acceptable depending on the case. As ChildRescue will be used to broadcast information concerning ongoing cases of missing children, the same danger also lurks; namely that ChildRescue will be used by abusers to locate missing children.” After that part, more information on two types of users’ registration, anonymous and named one, is provided. Do you believe that through these actions the risk is still valid?

Annex IV – Ethics Advisory Board comments mappings in D2.3

The current section shows how the comments of the Ethics Advisory Board are addressed in D2.3. For this reason, the subsections “Additional comments from EAB members” and “Table” which contain the comments of the EAB are provided with additional information of how each concern is addressed.

Addressing the additional comments from EAB members

In the following table we highlight how each comment in subsection “Additional comments from EAB members” in Annex III is addressed. The first column provides the exact extract from the subsection, while the second explains how the comment is being addressed.

Comment from the EAB (AB, EL)	How it is addressed
Clarify: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Purposes of processing; b. Retention policy (how long the data will be kept); c. Legal basis (GDPR, art. 6); d. Recipients of data; e. Categories of data 	D2.1 provides the workflows and the relevant dataflows of the procedures that are followed in the ChildRescue Platform. These workflows define the purpose of processing, the recipients of the data as well as the categories of the data. The legal basis is also enhanced in D2.3, in section 2.3.5. The retention policy is provided in the consent form.
Draw a simple diagram of the data flows which would include the aforementioned information (point 1). The data flows involved in the project are complex, ChildRescue and all stakeholders would benefit from a scheme/diagram which would foster clarity and transparency, and allows to better identify the privacy risks;	Already provided in D2.1. Additional information is also provided in D5.3. D2.3 uses D2.1 and D5.3 as input in order to define the security and privacy framework.
Include the notion of “accountability” (GDPR, art. 5.2) which is absent from the document despite being a foundational principle of the Regulation. More should be said about among other: the obligation to document the consent received; to document data breaches etc;	To be taken under consideration in the next iterations of WP1 (D1.4, D1.5) and WP2 (D2.4, D2.5).
In addition, ChildRescue will most likely need to keep a register of its processing activities (GDPR, art. 30), it would be advisable at this stage to already have a draft of this register even if it needs to be completed at a later stage;	To be taken under consideration in the next iterations of WP1 (D1.4) and WP2 (D2.4, D2.5).
Provide all the required information to the data subjects when their data are collected (GDPR, art. 13);	Not part of D2.3. To be taken under consideration during the ChildRescue Platform implementation in WP3.

Consider other potential legal basis (GDPR, art. 6) to process the missing children data than to obtain consent from the district attorney. As suggested, explore the public interest (GDPR, 6.2(e)) and vital interest grounds (GDPR, 6.2(d) and Recital 46);	Addressed in section 2.3.5
Define the roles of each actors (GDPR, art. 4(7)(8)). As explained during the call, the role of one actor can vary depending on the purposes for which the data is used;	To be defined in WP3.
Check the different Member states `rules concerning the use of national ID number, more researches should be done about the legal rules pertaining to that issue;	To be taken under consideration in the next iterations of WP1 (D1.4, D1.5) and WP2 (D2.4, D2.5).
Ground the use of GDPR, art. 23 on a precise legal basis as this provision can only be used under very strict conditions;	To be taken under consideration in the next iterations of WP1 (D1.4, D1.5) and WP2 (D2.4, D2.5).
Clarify throughout the text the distinction between "anonymisation" and "pseudonymisation". For instance, the statement: "When data expire, or consent is revoked, ChildRescue will provide the functionality to either remove the pseudonymised data or anonymise them" (WP2, point 2.3.2, p. 18) is not compliant. When the data served its purposes or the consent is withdrawn the only thing to do is either delete the data or anonymise them;	Addressed in 2.3.2.
Consider articles GDPR, 17.2 and 19, in case data subjects rights are exercised;	Concerning GDPR art. 17.2 and art. 19 there are no other data controllers apart from the ChildRescue Entity.

Comment from the EAB (PI)	How it is addressed
Regarding Requirement No. 2, the language used to specify, correlates with the specified use of the need for the data collection and the use of the data obtained. The clarification of a recipient's role will make clear what their function and legal requirements are. This addition will draw together the project's role, expectations	Added in the Consent Form, in "Annex II – Sample Consent Form"

<p>incumbent on recipient's as reflected in the relevant sections (2.2 and 2.3) of D2.3.</p> <p>Regarding Requirement No. 3, very strong efforts (reflected on policy and a procedure) would need to be made in order to obtain the consent of a child or of the parent who holds legal parental authority or of their legal guardian or, where the legal framework is structured in this way, of the statutory child protection agency responsible for the care of the child. A humanitarian agency may fall outside this process.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In extremis e.g. child protection issue/imminent risk of harm, data may be sought and shared. • The threshold for 'public interest' is very broad and different across states. Further thought and discussion and advice within and from the EAB be initiated to look specifically at a mechanism, which is GDPR and protection compliant. • The existing Missing children procedure, as detailed in the minutes, is strong, however may not be readily transferrable. 	<p>Addressed in section 3.3.5</p>
<p>Regarding Requirement No. 4, the risks of non-compliance should be included (examples to be specified e.g. 'screenshot' with sentence reflecting the list is not exhaustive) with a clear statement, requiring all data should be destroyed following the appropriate secure destruction method. It would be responsibility of ChildRescue to ensure this is clearly stated, however the responsibility to ensure destruction in all the situations outside ChildRescue core data collection, retention and destruction protocols, sits with those partners and or participating organisations who hold the data. This is also related to Requirement No. 7.</p>	<p>Added in the Consent Form, in "Annex II – Sample Consent Form". The user is informed about the obligations he/she has to fulfil as soon as the case is closed and the relevant data are removed.</p>
<p>Regarding Requirement No. 9, it is required to have a clear indication that the data subject can any time revoke their consent and that a relevant</p>	<p>Addressed in sections 3.3.3 and 3.3.5</p>

section will be added in the consent form. The process of what ChildRescue is going to do if someone asks for certain data to be erased, should be simply explained using terminology reflected in 2.2 with an additional chapter added to 2. Landscape analysis in privacy and anonymisation.	
Regarding Requirement No. 11, the process needs to be clearly detailed.	The user roles will be described in WP3 where all the specifications of the ChildRescue Platform will be defined.

Addressing the conclusions from the EAB telco

The table which lists the conclusions from the EAB has been extended with an additional column which explains how each conclusion has been addressed.

Table Annex IV-1: Ethics requirements list and conclusions from the EAB telco

2 nd Meeting EAB 12 th Sept 2018 Related Action: D7.1 to D7.12. Points of review with subsequent adjustment sign off	Related Section: Refer to <i>D2.3_Privacy and Anonymisation Methodological Foundations</i>	Conclusions from the 2 nd Meeting EAB	How it is addressed
D7.1 : GEN - Requirement No. 1 [12] A report by the Ethics Board must be submitted with the financial reports.		Not yet finalised	
D7.2 : H - Requirement No. 2 [3] 2.3. Templates of the informed consent forms and information sheet must be submitted.	D2.3 section 2.3.5	The reasons why ChildRescue processes the acquired data are very generic. A couple of sentences need to be added in the consent form. ChildRescue needs to be clear of the categories of the recipients that it could send the data. Check the section where ChildRescue is described as a processor and/or controller of the data.	Added in the Consent Form, in "Annex II – Sample Consent Form".

<p>D7.3 : H - Requirement No. 3 [3]</p> <p>2.5. The applicant must clarify how consent/assent will be ensured in case children and/or adults unable to give informed consent are involved.</p>	D2.3 section 2.3.5	Some members of the EAB thought that it is not enough to get the consent from the district attorney instead of directly the child. This can only be done if there are legal grounds such as public interest, or humanitarian urgency, etc.	Addressed in section 3.3.5
<p>D7.4 : H - Requirement No. 4 [3]</p> <p>Details must be provided about the measures taken to prevent the risk of enhancing vulnerability/stigmatisation of individuals/groups.</p>	D2.3 section 2.3.3, 2.3.4, 2.3.1	As long as ChildRescue can take this information back and there will not be any digital footprints, ChildRescue is fine. The notifications will be securely deleted from any device that were sent after they are not needed. Of course, the possibility of someone keeping a screenshot cannot be avoided.	Added in the Consent Form, in "Annex II – Sample Consent Form". The user is informed about the obligations he/she has to fulfil as soon as a case is closed and the relevant data are removed.
<p>D7.5 : H - Requirement No. 5 [3]</p> <p>2.8. Details on incidental findings policy must be provided.</p>		Not yet finalised	
<p>D7.6 : H - Requirement No. 6 [3]</p> <p>2.9. Copies of ethics approvals for the research with humans must be submitted.</p>		Not yet finalised	
<p>D7.7 : POPD - Requirement No. 7 [3]</p> <p>The applicant must explicitly confirm that the data used are publicly available. In case of data not publicly available, relevant authorisations must be provided.</p>	D2.3 section 2.3.3	ChildRescue must inform the recipients to whom ChildRescue has sent the data, in order they delete the data too. The only exemption to that is when this is impossible or it requires disproportionate effort (article 19 GDPR). ChildRescue should be ready to explain why it is impossible to do that.	Added in the Consent Form, in "Annex II – Sample Consent Form".
<p>D7.8 : POPD - Requirement No. 8 [3]</p> <p>4.1. Copies of opinion or confirmation by the competent Institutional Data Protection Officer and/or authorisation or notification by the National Data Protection Authority must be submitted (which</p>		Not yet finalised	

<p>ever applies according to the Data Protection Directive (EC Directive 95/46, currently under revision, and the national law).</p>			
<p>D7.9 : POPD - Requirement No. 9 [3] Detailed information must be provided on the procedures that will be implemented for data collection, storage, protection, retention and destruction and confirmation that they comply with national and EU legislation.</p> <p>The project intends to develop a mobile application. Details on the privacy policy and permissions must be provided (in this case, it is important to make sure that app users are aware that their data will be accessible by police authorities).</p> <p>The app also allows for real-time messaging among police forces and members of the community.</p> <p>In order to avoid wrongful information to be circulated, the dynamics of real-time messaging must be explained. In particular, it must be ensured that all information shared with the community is part of an ongoing investigation and has clearance to be disseminated among the public by a police or judicial body.</p> <p>The applicant has provided draft terms of use of the platform that indicate, for instance, that "You [app</p>	<p>D2.3 section 2.3.3 & section 2.3 intro</p> <p>D2.3 Section 2.3.5</p> <p>D2.3 section 2.1, section 2.2.3</p> <p>D2.3 section 2.3.4 and 2.2.2</p> <p>D2.3 section 2.3.3 (last paragraph) and 2.3.1</p>	<p>ChildRescue should have a good reason why specific data should be kept and it should be clearer about the data retention time period.</p> <p>ChildRescue should keep the data for as long it needs to in order to achieve its purpose.</p> <p>ChildRescue will describe a scenario where information will be kept available and used only if the case reopens.</p> <p>A clear indication that the data subject can any time revoke their consent will be added in the consent form.</p> <p>It is not clear what ChildRescue is going to do if someone asks for certain data to be erased. ChildRescue should be careful about the pseudonymisation and anonymisation. Pseudonymisation takes place when a case is closed. Anonymisation is equal to deletion and it happens after ChildRescue is certain that the case won't be reopened.</p>	<p>Addressed in sections 3.3.3 and 3.3.5</p> <p>To be provided in D1.4</p> <p>Added in the Consent Form, in "Annex II – Sample Consent Form".</p> <p>Addressed in sections 3.3.3 and 3.3.5</p> <p>To be taken under consideration during the implementation of WP3.</p>

<p>user] are solely responsible for your conduct and any data, text, information, screen names, graphics, photos, profiles, audio and video clips, links ("Content") that you submit, post, and display on the ChildRescue service." This is unacceptable as all content would need to be reviewed before being shared. The burden of the potential harmful uses of the platform must fall on the developer/owner, not the user (who can be warned, but not be made responsible).</p> <p>The app will allow for users to register anonymously. While their public identity can be anonymous, police forces should always be able to identify who is providing evidence related to an open case. Many countries forbid anonymous police reports, for instance. The legality and ethics of this point must be clarified.</p> <p>Details on robust data deletion mechanisms (including meta data) once a user decided to leave the platform need to be provided.</p>		<p>ChildRescue needs to be clear towards the people giving the consent that they have the right to have the collected data deleted. Section 2.3.4 and everything that is related to the article 17 GDPR i.e. the right to erasure needs to be finetuned a little bit more.</p> <p>If the data are already in pseudonymised form, and the data subject asks the deletion of the data, ChildRescue must either delete or anonymise the data.</p>	<p>Added in the Consent Form, in "Annex II – Sample Consent Form".</p>
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			Addressed 3.3.3 in sections and 3.3.5
<p>D7.10 : POPD - Requirement No. 10 [6]</p> <p>The project intends to develop predictive algorithms. A detailed description of the data these will use and the assumptions they will make need to be independently assessed.</p>	Section 2.3.5 D2.3 not yet covered	It is not possible to be covered at this project's phase.	
<p>D7.11 : OEI - Requirement No. 11 [3]</p> <p>The project will encourage citizens to contribute to an ongoing investigation, and thus to act as members of the police force. This has led to cases of mob justice or individuals taking matters into their own hands. The steps taken to ensure that those using the app are aware of what their role is, where it begins and where it ends, need to be provided.</p>	D2.3 section 2.3.4 not fully covered	<p>ChildRescue will provide extended information in several layers that start from the anonymous users, to the registered eponymous users, to the validated volunteers, and the members of the administrative team of the NGOs that handle the cases. There will be several levels of access.</p> <p>It is fine to provide different information depending on the level of identification. The volunteer organisations will validate the users through a know your customer procedure.</p>	The user roles will be described in WP3 where all the specifications of the ChildRescue Platform will be defined.
<p>D7.12: OEI - Requirement No. 12 [3]</p> <p>The app may be misused by people who intend to locate missing children to abuse them. Details on how this will be avoided must be provided.</p>	Section 2.3.4 d2.3	ChildRescue won't provide more information than it is already disseminated with for instance, Amber Alert, but there is always the possibility of misuse of the platform, like it may happen with an Amber Alert. ChildRescue will follow the common practice.	The "Know your customer" methodology provided in section is a first measure against intentional misuse of the platform.